

CARDEA

Career Acknowledgement for Research (Managers) Delivering for the European Area Grant Agreement No. 101058572

Training Catalogue - Mid Term Update – D. 7.2

Funded by the European Union

The CARDEA project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor REA can be held responsible for them.

Training Catalogue - Mid Term Update – D. 7.2	
CARDEA - Career Acknowledgement for Research (Managers) Delivering for the European Area	
Project acronym	CARDEA
Grant No	101058572
Call identifier	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-20
Start of project	1st June 2022
Duration	48 months
Deliverable no	D7.2
Work Package	WP7
Authors	Barbara Chiuconi Erica Feliziani Francesca Spigarelli
Work Package/Task leader	University of Macerata

CARDEA MATRIX

INDEX

Abstract	5
ACRONYMS	6
Project team	7
Governance	9
1 – Introduction	10
2 - The EU context	13
3 - Training ecosystem for Research Managers	15
3.1 The scenario depicted by surveys targeting Research Managers	15
3.1.1 CARDEA survey	15
3.1.2 RAAAP surveys.....	20
3.1.3 HETFA survey	25
3.1.4 EARMA PDRC survey.....	29
3.1.5 Other surveys	31
3.1.6 Main findings from the surveys.....	32
3.2 Training opportunities for Research Managers.....	33
3.2.1 Certified training for Research Managers	33
3.2.2 EU and international training projects and initiatives for Research Managers	35
3.2.3 Main academic training for Research Managers.....	36
3.3 Breaking the barriers: Research Managers’ skills based on the perspective of the “others”	38
3.3.1 The perspective of policy makers.....	38
3.3.2 The perspective of Research Managers’ employers	41
Context	41
Methodology	42
Results	42
Conclusions.....	53
3.3.3 The perspective of opinion leaders	55
Context	55
Methodology	55
Results	56
Conclusions.....	60
4 - CARDEA training modules: how they are implemented	62
4.1 Target.....	62
4.2 Format	63

4.3 Content.....	63
4.4 Trainers.....	66
4.5 Micro-credentials	66
4.6 CARDEA training modules syllabus.....	66
REFERENCES	84

Abstract

Cardea is the Roman Goddess of door pivots, ideal to describe our project to develop Research Managers (RM) who strengthen Europe's R&I excellence through a diverse set of support roles and responsibilities. Research Management as a profession is almost invisible from policy, career progression and tenure opportunities across Europe. Also, there is little consistency between countries, funders, policymakers and individual institutions. Cardea will develop supports to address this inequality. Our consortium has enjoyed considerable success doing this for Researchers already. We will create a detailed data-driven (500+ participants, 24 countries) knowledge space-defining and characterising the problem. Based on this, we will develop a range of solutions, including a Capacity Maturity Model to assess and improve RM activities and a novel RM Hub for networking and training to include a community of practice. Equality, Diversity and Inclusion, Widening Participation (EU13), and Public-Private partnership actions will be at the core of our research, training and enhancement activities. Additionally, the mobility and networking of RM and those with responsibility for developing RMs will be included to ensure the RM ecosystem grows transnationally. We will learn from each other and support one another in bringing RM careers to the next level. Significantly these actions will provide a significant evidence base to advocate the inclusion of RM exigences in policy, and we will target this proactively, targeting 38 key decision-making organisations. Amongst the impacts of Cardea will be an enduring network and Hub that can facilitate RM development and collaboration, a validated methodology to assess RM careers and a well-established baseline against which improvements can be objectively measured. This allows us to develop an RM Charter and offer a Concordat to institutions and organisations that make significant commitments to developing RM activities in a structured, mature manner.

ACRONYMS

ARMA	Association of Research managers Administrators	HSS	Humanities and Social Sciences
Cardea	Career Acknowledgement for Research (Managers) Delivering for the European Area. Also Cardea is the Roman Goddess of the hinge, door pivot, the name embodies the role of RM as door openers and facilitators of access to research	EIRMA	European Industrial Research management Association
C&C	HRS4R Charter and Code for Researchers	IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
CERMH	Cardea European Research Managers Hub	IOP	Institute of Physics
DOI	Digital Object Identifier	KSA	Knowledge, Skills and Abilities
EARMA	European Association of Research Managers and Administrators	KT	Knowledge Transfer
EDI	Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion	NORDP	National Organisation of Research Development Professionals
EIRMA	European Industrial Research Management Association	OER	Open Educational Resources
ERA	European Research Area	PESTLE	Political, Economic, Societal, Technological, Legal, Environmental
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation	R&I	Research and Innovation
HC	Human Capital	RISE	Realizing Integration through Social Enterprise
HE	Horizon Europe	RM(s)	Research Manager(s)
HEI	Higher Educational Institution	RPO(s)	Research Performing Organisation(s)
HR	Human Resources	SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
HRS4R	Human Resource Strategy for Researchers	SES	Socio-Economic Status
		STE(A)M	Science, Technology, Engineering (Arts) and Maths
		T&L	Teaching and Learning
		TNA	Training Needs Analysis

Project team

The consortium consists of thought leaders and active practitioners in research management and, in particular, the team have expertise in the organisational support and professional development of research managers. Members of the consortium have previously worked together successfully on related projects through the HR excellence in Research award and have established an informal network for collaboration on a range of Pan-European activities.

The project coordinator is Mary Kate O'Regan.

University College Cork

UCC is an award-winning institution with a history of independent thinking stretching back over 170 years. UCC is proud to be ranked in the top 2% of universities in the world with a student population of over 22,500. UCC is an internationally competitive, research-led university that plays a key role in the development of Ireland's knowledge-based economy. Its institutional research strategy focuses on creating and supporting world-leading clusters of researchers, building on the research strengths of the University. In 2022, UCC generated €105M in research income and collaborated with over 4,284 research entities in 140 countries.

CERTH

CERTH is a legal non-profit governmental entity organised under private law, under the auspices of the General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT) of the Greek Ministry of Education, Research and Religious Affairs. CERTH's mission is to carry out basic and applied research with special emphasis in developing new products and services with industrial, economic and social impact. In the last three years, CERTH participated in or coordinated almost 300 active research projects

UNIMC

The University of Macerata (UNIMC) - founded in 1290 - is among the oldest universities in Italy and the only one to have a focus entirely on humanities and socio-economic sciences (SSHs). University's motto "Humanism that innovates" illustrates its mission: to contribute to the development of people and society through the added value that social and human sciences bring to the understanding of complex socioeconomic and political issues, according to an interdisciplinary perspective.

UNIPU

University of Pula started its mission in 2006, but it includes entities that exist from the 1960s. It is organised into several constituent departments based on the principle of integrated structure. It has 240 staff in total and 3,600 students enrolled. Located in a 3,000 years old town situated in the South of Istria, the most evolved region in Croatia and with a distinct cultural diversity due to its geographical position and historical heritage. The University carries out a distinctive blend of research areas particularly valuable when mixed together creating a new perspective of mutual sharing and learning.

ULIEGE

With over 5000 researchers, 43 research units, 150 active Spin-offs, and over 2100 research agreements, the University of Liege is committed to the development and successful advancement of its research leaders. In an effort to best support the research community, ULiege has several projects in place to support research unit managers, doctoral supervisors, senior post-doctoral researchers and aspiring doctoral candidates.

IFJ PAN

The Henryk Niewodniczański Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences (IFJ PAN) is one of the largest research institutes of the Polish Academy of Sciences, awarded the highest A+ Category in science and engineering and the HR Excellence in Research. IFJ PAN conducts fundamental and applied research in the field of physics and related sciences.

UPB

University Politehnica of Bucharest is the largest (30 000 students) technical university in Romania, with a tradition developed over 200 years. MicroDERLab is a Research Group at UPB, promoting a common research agenda on electrical engineering topics. MicroDERLab interdisciplinary team is actively involved in European and nationally funded R&D projects, one of the main objectives being to design holistic solutions to be supported by visionary energy policies and regulatory framework. Members of MicroDERLab have a wide experience on R&D management in various contexts, following their stages abroad in Erasmus+, Fulbright, DAAD and other exchange programs.

AGAUR

AGAUR is a public funding organization (Catalan Government Agency) responsible for implementing policies addressed to University & Research Community in Catalonia created by Law 7/2001 within the Ministry/Department of Research and Universities, Generalitat de Catalunya.

AGAUR implements higher education and research policies through scholarships, grants and loans, to provide access to University studies, research and knowledge transfer in Catalonia; through a peer-review assessment. The funding activity of AGAUR involves the annual allocation of over 200 M€ in aprox. 30 Grant programmes.

Governance

The Cardea consortium is supported by an advisory board. The board consist of 14 experts, including international advisors (including extra-EU membership, Research Management representative groups (e.g. EARMA), Senior institutional leaders (e.g. University HR managers) and Private industry.

The board will support the team through expert advice, new ideas and mentorship.

Name	Organisation
Dr Conor O'Carroll (Chair)	SciPol Services Ltd
Professor Adrian Cura	Politehnica University of Bucharest (Professor of Research Management)
Dr. Ing. Agr. Miguel Sierra Pereiro	INIA Innovation and Communication Manager (Uruguay).
Dr Gillian Bruton	Senior Research Manager MaREI Research Centre UCC
Dr Joanne Ui Chruialaoich	Manager of the Food Industry Training Unit UCC
Dr Isabelle Halleux	Consultant supporting research governance and projects in Belgium
Professor Dimitris Deniozos	Advisor to the General Secretary of Public Investment and NSRF/Partnership Agreement of Greece. Elected assistant professor at the Technical University of Crete, Department of Production and Management Engineering.
Dr George Papamichail	Director Science & Technology Park of Crete Greece
Loredana Marmora	Senior Project Manager ISINNOVA
Dr Eoin Sherwin	Associate Director Publications Strategy Eli Lilly and Company
Dr Gabi Lombardo	European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities Expert in both higher education and global research policy.
Doris Alexander	Associate Director of European Engagement, Trinity College Dublin
Dr Olaf Svenningsen	EARMA's Senior Project Liaison for RM-ROADMAP
Mary Twomey	Deputy Director/Assistant Principal Officer, Innovation, Research and Development Policy, Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science Government of Ireland

1 – Introduction

CARDEA project in a nutshell

CARDEA: Career Acknowledgement for Research Managers Delivering for the European Area is a Horizon Europe funded project. Its overall goal is to contribute to the recognition, promotion and professionalisation of Research Managers (RMs) roles, by outlining skills requirements, career pathways and appropriate developmental supports and recognition for those who choose this career.

More specifically, CARDEA will:

- Increase awareness amongst research management staff about existing training, networking and mobility opportunities at EU, national, and regional levels;
- Grow the capacity and compatibility of cooperation and funding systems throughout the European Research Area for research management, and support to scientists;
- Improve knowledge for policymaking about the training and networking patterns of research support staff and research management;
- Improve awareness of the EU policy drivers and the EU research peculiarity in the Higher Education Institutions and Research organisations;
- Establish central hubs to provide the EU research system with the most appropriate “fit for purpose” skills in EU research management, with active involvement of entities located in widening countries;
- Provide recommendations aiming at facilitating a clear career path for RMs at national and EU levels, enhancing their role towards the achievement of the new European Research Area objectives.

The project will contribute to Action 17 of the ERA policy agenda¹ “Enhance the strategic capacity of Europe’s public research performing and funding organisations”, which aims to improve the European R&I system across the entire ERA, by strengthening the capacity for research management in Europe’s public research performing and funding organisations. Therefore, CARDEA is a key component of the so called “Research management initiative”, launched by the EU Commission to enhance:

- **Upskilling:** improve training and skills of research management staff
- **Recognition:** contribute to professionalization
- **Networking:** support best-practice exchange
- **Capacity building:** support less R&I intense regions and organisations

Deliverable 7.2

Among the 9 work packages composing the CARDEA work plan, WP 7 “Training and development” aims to develop a comprehensive training programme designed by and for RMs, based on a deep analysis of RMs needs performed within the project.

The present deliverable, D7.2, is an update of deliverable D7.1 “Training Catalogue – Initial suite”. Both of them are available in open access within the Cardea community² in Zenodo. D7.2 reports on the training needs for RMs, outlines the main training initiatives available for RMs and illustrates the concept idea and syllabus of the CARDEA training modules, expected to be launched in November 2024 (M30).

As for the methodology used, CARDEA investigated RMs’ training needs via a two-fold analysis:

1. Analysis of the results emerged by EU and international surveys conducted in recent years and targeting RMs. Goal of this analysis was to gain a full understanding of training needs from the RMs’ point of view.
2. Analysis of the needs and expectations placed on RMs from other key actors of the Research and Innovation systems placed on RMs from: RM’s employers, policy makers in the field of research and

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-area_en

² <https://zenodo.org/records/10731538>

innovation, opinion leaders. The goal of this analysis was to understand training needs from the perspective of those who are interested in the enhancement of the support provided by RMs. This second component of the methodology, less usual than the first one, was not explicitly foreseen in the Annex I of CARDEA, but it was necessary to avoid results that are self-referential (i.e. coming only from RMs).

D7.2 provides also an **overview of the main training opportunities available to RMs**, highlighting:

- Available certified training options;
- Major RM associations and networks that offer diverse, though often uncertified, training;
- Various EU and international initiatives for RM skill development, and
- Academic programs relevant to RMs.

Moreover CARDEA, in collaboration with the RM ROADMAP project³, has created an integrated online tool—a searchable repository on the CARDEA website⁴. This dashboard provides RMs with easy access to up-to-date information on training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities across the ERA.

These analyses were very useful to describe the main features, needs, gaps related to the training ecosystem for RMs in Europe. Therefore, they were the starting point for designing the CARDEA training modules. Moreover, they can be useful to others that have the same need to develop a training path for RMs and that from this analysis could get precious information.

Once the training needs and ecosystem of RMs were analysed by WP7, CARDEA consortium developed training modules specifically targeting RMs. D7.2 presents an **overview and the syllabus of the training modules that CARDEA had developed**.

The learning objectives of CARDEA module is to furnish training for RMs covering all competence areas of the profession. The CARDEA training was shaped following the learning outcomes and the competences included into the [CARDEA RM Competences Framework](#)⁵. The CARDEA modules are a comprehensive training **covering the main aspect of research management profession**.

The main **targets of the CARDEA training are RM1** - First Stage Research Manager (newcomers in the profession) according to the Profile Framework for Research Manager Careers⁶ (RM1-RM2). Indeed, currently the labor market is actively seeking RMs, and there is a strong need to develop training programs that prepare new and specialized labor force as RMs. CARDEA training offers support to employers that otherwise have to rely on different training providers and spend time and effort to train new colleagues. Being the target of CARDEA training, mainly the category of RM1, the CARDEA modules focus on **foundational level competences of the RM Comp**. However, the training could also be useful for more senior staff who are willing to deepen their understanding of a particular aspect of the research management profession that they are not very familiar with.

The CARDEA training modules consists of **17 free recorded lessons** that are uploaded in the **CARDEA HUB**, a virtual space dedicated to training and networking of the European RMs.

The CARDEA training modules are part of the **CARDEA Academy initiative**⁷, which has the goal to address the specific needs of RMs by offering various programs, resources, and toolkits to help RMs develop and advance

³ <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/competenceframework/>

⁵

<https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/support/hrresearch/CARDEAFrameworkRM1toRM4CompetencyFrameworkJan10th2024.pdf>

⁶ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/competenceframework/>

⁷ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/cardeaacademy/>

their careers. The Academy particularly aims to engage RMs from Widening Countries and leverages connections through HR Excellence in Research and EURAXESS to broaden its reach.

The format of recorded lessons was chosen because of its flexibility and **inclusivity**. Participation through on-line webinars allows all potential participants to enjoy for free the training on-demand, without sustaining other costs related to travel and accommodation. The choice of recorded lessons in such a way open the audience to RMs that are at the beginning of their career and could not have specific funds available dedicated for training (this is often the case of RMs from Widening countries or from small organisations, e.g. associations, NGOs).

The attendance of the CARDEA training path is certified through the free **release of micro-credential** which is an inter-operable and international proof of the acquired competences during the learning path, a document that can be presented during hiring processes, career progression procedures, or when starting a new job position.

A detailed description of the CARDEA training modules and the work behind them is reported in paragraph 4.6 with is a syllabus of all the 17 modules, specifying the content of each module and video.

Among the 17 modules, one innovative module is dealing with the use of **Artificial Intelligence in the research management context**, that currently, in autumn 2024, is a pioneering offer, considering the scarcity of training opportunities targeting RMs on such new, revolutionary, and fast-evolving topic.

2 - The EU context

The **ERA (European Research Area)** was launched in 2000 with the aim to build a common scientific and technological area for the EU where the creation of a single market for research and innovation is fostering free movement of researchers, scientific knowledge and innovation, and encouraging a more competitive European industry. Over 20 years, the ERA has seen major achievements such as the diffusion of research infrastructures, as well as the implementation of open science principles, international cooperation, gender balance in research and innovation, joint programming, research careers and the mobility of researchers. On 30 September 2020, the Commission adopted a Communication on '**A New ERA for Research and Innovation**'⁸, in which it proposes a revitalization of ERA, sets out a new vision and calls for mobilising Member States around key principles and values for identifying shared priority areas for action.

The Council Conclusions on the New ERA, adopted on 1 December 2020⁹, called on the Member States and the Commission to develop in 2021 an **ERA policy agenda**¹⁰ and a multi-level governance model to deliver on the new ambition for the ERA. The ERA Policy Agenda, launched in November 2021¹¹, set out voluntary ERA actions for the period 2022-2024 to contribute to the priority areas defined in the Council Recommendation on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe. 20 actions organized in 4 priority areas (1 - deepening a truly functioning internal market for knowledge; 2 - taking up together the challenges posed by the twin green and digital transition, and increasing society's participation in the ERA; 3 - amplifying access to research and innovation excellence across the union; 4 - advancing concerted research and innovation investments and reforms) were proposed.

Among the 20 actions of the ERA Policy Agenda, for the **ERA action 17** "Enhance the strategic capacity of Europe's public research performing organisations", a **Science Management Initiative** was proposed to improve training and skills development of science management staff. This action intended to pilot a **European network for research and innovation managers** through Horizon Europe, explore European training and certification programmes, and provide policy support for Member States through mutual learning platforms on science management. The ERA 17 policy action works across four priority axes: 1) **Upskilling**, to improve training and skills of research management staff, 2) **Networking**, to support best-practice exchange, 3) **Recognition**, to contribute to RM professionalization, and 4) **Capacity building**, to support less R&I intense regions and organizations. Under the umbrella of Action 17, within the Horizon Europe work programme 2021-2022, the call HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-20 "Towards a Europe-wide training and networking scheme for Research Managers" funded the CARDEA and RM ROAD MAP projects aimed to achieve the 4 priority axes of ERA action 17.

The need of upskilling for research management staff is in line with the empowerment of training and lifelong learning enshrined in the **European Skills Agenda**¹², launched in July 2020. The agenda sets ambitious, quantitative objectives for upskilling (improving existing skills) and reskilling (training in new skills) to be achieved within the period 2020-2025, through 12 actions. The implementation of these actions is further promoted via the launch of the initiative of **2023 European Year of Skills**¹³, whose aim was to make sure that European workforce skills are relevant for labour market needs. Member States have endorsed the EU 2030

⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-area_en

⁹ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13567-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

¹⁰ https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf

¹¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/1a0df8ff-5313-11ec-91ac-01aa75ed71a1>

¹² <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=89&newsId=9723&furtherNews=yes#navItem-1>

¹³ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-year-skills-2023_en

social targets that at least 60% of adults should participate in training every year, already presenting their national contribution to meeting this target.

Among its 12 flagship actions of the European Skills Agenda, new initiative on a European **approach to micro-credentials**¹⁴ aims to support the quality, transparency and take-up of micro-credentials across the EU, in order to encourage people to upskill and reskill in a fast and effective way, in line with needs of the labor market and a fast-changing society. The micro-credentials answer to the need to reskill and upskill through more flexible alternatives than a full degree in order to overcome the gap between the learning outcomes of initial formal qualifications and emerging skills needs in the labor market.

¹⁴ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document-library-docs/european-approach-micro-credentials-higher-education-consultation-group-output-final-report.pdf>

3 - Training ecosystem for Research Managers

3.1 The scenario depicted by surveys targeting Research Managers

As starting point of CARDEA deliverables, a desk research was conducted to analyse the results of the main available surveys targeting RMs and investigating the ecosystem where RMs operate. Indeed, these surveys depict some aspects related to the training ecosystem for RMs. In particular, the analysis focuses on 5 surveys, namely CARDEA, first (2016) and second (2019) RAAAP, HETFA and EARMA surveys, and mentions some others.

These surveys were developed in different contexts and for different purposes, but all of them give an insight into the subject of training for RMs. The common characteristic of them is the fact that the participants of the surveys are RMs. Per each survey, an introductory paragraph to the context of the survey is provided, followed by an “identikit” of the respondents to the questionnaires (country, age, gender, education, and other relevant info) and then by a summary of the main findings concerning the training.

Just as clarification, the 5 surveys refer in some cases to soft skills, in some others refer to transversal skills. For the purpose of this deliverable, these words are used as synonymous.

3.1.1 CARDEA survey

Context of the survey

As a starting point of CARDEA project, it was first necessary to develop a detailed understanding of the contexts, challenges and opportunities that RMs face within and beyond the EU. Indeed, the CARDEA proposal was built according to a two-stage model. The goal of Stage 1 was to establish a solid data driven baseline of evidence to inform project activities, as there was little systematic data available about the needs and challenges of RMs. While Stage 2’ aim was to inform the development of solutions to meet the challenges.

The CARDEA survey belongs to stage 1’s actions. It consisted of a questionnaire of 97 items organized in 11 sections to ask RMs about their demographics, employment, skills and education, motivation and satisfaction and professional networks and mobility. The survey was launched in August 2022 and was open till the end of December 2022. Each of the CARDEA partners reserved the utmost commitment to widespread the survey through national and international associations of RMs, specific networks and own contacts and channels.

A specific CARDEA report¹⁵ summarizes the main results of the survey. In addition, all the questions of the CARDEA survey together with the raw data are available in Zenodo¹⁶ (Chrualaoich and O’Regan, 2023). This section 3.1.1 collects and comments the main results concerning “training ecosystem for RMs”.

Survey respondents

The CARDEA survey targeted the RM’s community. In total, 855 responses were received. The 45,5% of respondents (389 responses) completed the entire survey in all 11 sections. 456 respondents completed at least nine of the sections (more than 50% of the total respondents).

Table 1 furnishes a summary of the main characteristics of the respondents that provided the information of CARDEA survey.

Table 1. Main characteristics of respondents of the CARDEA survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 73.2%
Age	Average age: 43 years Age groups: - 29 and under: 4.5%

¹⁵ https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/research/cardea/Cardea_Report_Summary_FINAL_Discl.pdf

¹⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/7882908#.ZE-Edc7MKHs>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30-39: 28.5% - 40-49: 47.1% - 50-59: 17.6% - 60 and over: 2.3%
Countries	EU Nationals: 86.5% <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ireland: 17.7% - Spain: 16.3% - Portugal: 12.2% - Italy: 11.2% - Germany: 8% - Poland: 5.5% - Croatia: 4.3% - France: 3.1% - Belgium: 3% Other EU: 5.5% UK and Northern Ireland: 3% Rest of world: 4.9%
Education	PhD: 53.9% PhD and master: 90.8% Specific RM qualification: 19% Knows 2 languages: 79.1%
Years of experiences as RM	Over 10 years: 33% At least 6 years: 21% 4-6 years: 12% Less than 4 years: 34%
Other info	Work and live in country of birth: 87.6% Member of a professional RM Association: 42.5% Type of contract Permanent: 66% Fixed Term: 34%

Less than ten percent of respondents ($n = 49$) are dedicated to managing an individual project. Over a third of respondents ($n = 186$, 35.0%) provide specialised professional services to a range of projects, with a further $n = 67$ (12.6%) leading a team that provides specialised professional services to a range of research projects.

Main results concerning trainings

RM professional qualification

Participants to CARDEA questionnaire were asked about their research management and administration professional qualifications. 81.0% ($n = 460$) of respondents do not have any specific research management qualifications or certifications. The remaining 19.0% ($n = 108$) report a range of credentials, with the most popular shown in table 2. It is worth to point out that there is no significant relationship between professional qualifications and the highest level of educational achievement.

Table 2. Most popular RM certifications as emerged from CARDEA survey

Certification	n
Masters in Research Administration	26
Certificate in Research Management (CRM)	22
Bachelors in Research Management	8
Certificate in Leadership of Research Management	8
Certificate in Research Administration (CRA)	6

In addition to RM-specific certifications, participants were given a free text area to indicate other qualifications that support or assist them in research management activities. Many people indicated that their expertise in research management derived from experience of actively doing the job. In addition,

several respondents referenced project management training from short courses to full master in project management. Prince2¹⁷ was the most frequent framework mentioned. Finally, a small number of respondents indicated that training in English language and career development was a feature of their educational profile.

RM's skills

Within CARDEA survey the participants were asked to rate the importance of specific skills for an effective research management activity and whether they had been offered training in these skills. Respondents chose among a list of 90 skills, that were grouped into 9 families, based on a comprehensive review of the literature on research management and RM roles (see table 3).

Per each of the 90 skills, the participants were asked to value the importance of the skill for research management within a scale ranging from 1 "not at all important" to 5 "vital" and to indicate whether training concerning this specific skill has been available or not.

Table 3 reports the averages of the importance estimated by the respondents for the 9 skill families and the relative percentage of cases in which training has been available. It is interesting to note that albeit transversal skills are the ones perceived as most important for daily work for research management, in the meantime, they are perceived as the less trained. On the other side, a lot of training opportunities are available concerning "specialised knowledge for research performing organisational contexts", which is perceived as less important among the 9 families. These findings corroborate the ones reported by Tauginiene (2009) according to which transversal skills, such as problem solving and communications capabilities, are among the main skills and qualities that a RM should possess.

Table 3. The 9 skill families of CARDEA survey with the rating of importance and occurrence of training

Skill family	Mean of Importance for research management (from 1 "not at all important" to 5 "vital")	Available training (% of the cases)
Transversal skills	4,26	10
Relationship management	4,15	14
Project Management	4,12	28
Financing/Contracting/Compliance	3,97	22
Communication	3,87	17
Line management and supervision of others	3,81	14
Outreach and community	3,79	11
Technical skills	3,72	19
Specialised knowledge	3,66	50

Table 4 reports in cardinal order the 25 skills out of the total 90, that are perceived as most important AND in the meantime as the ones for which less training opportunities are available. Indeed, this ranking score is the result of the sum of two ranking scores, one categorizing the skill importance (from most important to less) and one categorizing the available training (from less available to most available). Again, it is worth to notice that the transversal skills including reliability, attention to detail, flexibility, proactivity, autonomy, problem-solving and efficiency, are placed on the top of the list. Moreover, among the other top-25 skills there are skills that, albeit they are not classified as transversal skills, can be assimilated to transversal skills as they are part of the relationship and communication sphere i.e. building trust within partnerships; collaborating for success; building and maintaining relationships with funders, partners or other stakeholders; networking; academic and community relationship support; teamwork; responsibility for engaging with key stakeholders; coordination of communication.

Table 4. Top-25 important skills according to CARDEA deliverable and their skill family of belonging

¹⁷ <https://www.prince2.com/eur>

Cardinal position	Skill	Skill family
1	Reliability	Transversal skills
2	Attention to detail	Transversal skills
3	Flexibility	Transversal skills
4	Proactivity	Transversal skills
5	Autonomy	Transversal skills
6	Problem-solving	Transversal skills
7	Efficiency	Transversal skills
8	Building trust within partnerships	Relationship management
9	Collaborating for success	Relationship management
10	Critical thinking	Transversal skills
11	Openness	Transversal skills
12	Building and maintaining relationships with funders, partners or other stakeholders	Communication
13	Diversified knowledge set	Transversal skills
14	Decision making	Transversal skills
15	Motivation	Transversal skills
16	Strategic thinking	Transversal skills
17	Managing competing demands	Relationship management
18	Networking	Relationship management
19	Academic and community relationship support	Outreach and community
20	Values Appreciation	Transversal skills
21	Teamwork	Relationship management
22	Responsibility for engaging with key stakeholders	Outreach and community
23	Coordination of communication	Communication
24	Creativity	Transversal skills
25	Promoting or supporting mutual learning	Relationship management

Professional Development Plans and Continuing Professional Development

The questionnaire examined whether RMs have Professional Development Plans (PDPs), whether they engage in Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and asked about the kind of support that would be useful in a research management context. The core findings are shown in

Table 5.

Table 5. Key professional development data from CARDEA survey

	n	%
Do you have a PDP?*		
Yes, personal	164	40.2
Yes, institutional	77	16.0
Yes, from funding agency	3	0.6
Yes, a national initiative	2	0.4
No	220	45.8
Other	14	2.9
Have you undertaken any CPD in the last 12 months		
Yes, during working hours	168	35.8
Yes, on personal time	106	22.6
No	195	41.6
If you have completed CPD in the last year, how much time have you devoted to this		
None	23	8.8

<8 hours	41	15.6
9-40 hours	146	55.7
41-80 hours	20	7.6
>81 hours	30	11.5

**Note the values do not add up to 100% as several people have more than one type of PDP.*

Participants ($n = 480$) were asked if they had a PDP. Over half (51.2%) do have at least one type of PDP, with many respondents indicating they have more than one. The most popular PDP is a personal plan (40.2%), and the next most popular type of PDP is an institutional plan (16.0%). Less than 1% of respondents have a PDP linked to a funding agency or as part of a national initiative. The data suggest that RMs are twice as likely to have an individual PDP rather than one provided or supported by their employer or national level. While this reflects the proactivity and engagement of the cohort, it challenges a systematic approach to research management development. Additionally, 45.8% of respondents ($n = 220$) have no PDP at all. In the free text area, several participants indicated that this is topic that their institution is currently examining.

Participants were then asked about their engagement with CPD. 58.4% of respondents ($n = 274$) have engaged in CPD in the last year. This value is very close to the EU 2030 target that 60% of the adult population should be involved in lifelong learning and is substantially above the average engagement in lifelong learning by professionals¹⁸. This is an encouraging result that shows that RMs are invested in and proactive about learning. For those that have engaged in CPD, 35.8% ($n = 168$) have undertaken CPD during work hours, and 22.6% ($n = 106$) have engaged in learning on their personal time. 41.6% ($n = 195$) have not engaged in CPD in the last year.

Participants were also asked to identify other type of support that could be beneficial to completing research management responsibilities. Eighty responses were collected to this query, the highest response rate for a free text area in this survey. Several themes emerged. There was a strong indication that research management is under-resourced from a staffing and facilities perspective. Other respondents talked about networking – existing or potential. Two types of networking were identified. The first was developing a community of practice within the research management ecosystem; this type of approach would enable sharing of expertise and experience. The second was a structured way to facilitate collaboration between RMs and other relevant stakeholders (e.g. national contact points). The final theme that was identified was the continued need to recognition of research management as an established, defined career.

¹⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/DDN-20190517-1>

3.1.2 RAAAP surveys

Context of the surveys

The RAAAP (Research Administration As A Profession) taskforce was created to periodically survey RMs and collect and analyse data about the evolution of the profession at global level.

The first RAAAP survey was held in 2016, the second edition in 2019 and the third in 2022. The 2016 survey was funded by the United States National Council of University Research Administrators¹⁹ (NCURA) and was led by Simon Kerridge (University of Kent, UK) and Stephanie Scott (Columbia University, USA) as Co-PIs, and was supported by an international advisory group. In June 2018, the Council of the International Network of Research Management Societies²⁰ (INORMS) formally endorsed the RAAAP survey as an INORMS initiative. The task force initially included many members of the 2016 RAAAP survey team. In the following years, it expanded to include representatives from each of the INORMS associations and also some other related associations.

In order to describe the evolution of some aspects of the profession over the years, a core section of the questionnaire asks the same questions in every survey. Other parts of the questionnaire change, focusing on specific subjects of particular relevance at the time. For example, the focus of the 2019 survey was “research impact”, while the focus of the third survey was “how I became a research manager and administrator”. The questionnaires and the raw data are available as open resources on “Figshare”²¹.

This section analyzes the results of the 2016 and 2019 surveys only.

Survey respondents

In Kerridge and Scott (2018), it is pointed out that the RAAAP survey targeted only RMs that were association members, and it should be assumed that, generally, those who responded are members of (at least one) RM association.

For the 2016 survey, overall 2,691 responses were collected, from 64 countries; however only 19 countries had more than 10 responses, and 5 (Australia, Canada, Norway, UK, and the USA) had over 100 responses. While, in the 2019 survey, 4,325 research management and administration professionals responded from over 70 countries around the globe. It is important to note that, in both RAAAP editions, most of respondents were from the Anglo-Saxon countries and consequently the surveys’ results mainly reflect their views and could be less relevant for the European context.

The following two tables (table 6 and 7) furnish a summary of the main characteristics of the respondents respectively for the 2016 and 2019 surveys.

Table 6 – Main characteristics of respondents of the 2016 RAAAP survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 77%
Age	Age groups: - 24 and under: 0.4% - 25-34: 14.7% - 35-44: 32.2% - 45-54: 31%

¹⁹ <https://www.ncura.edu/>

²⁰ <https://inorms.net/>

²¹ The results of the 2016 survey are available at the following link: https://figshare.com/collections/RAAAP_Research_Administration_around_the_Profession_data_sets_and_supporting_files/4022284 (consulted on April 2023); the results of the 2019 survey are available at the following link: https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/RAAAP-2_Datasets_17_linked_datasets_/18972935 (consulted on April 2023).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 55-64: 18.6% - 65 and over: 2.3% - Prefer not to provide: 0.7%
Countries	United States of America: 36.87% Europe (excl UK): 15.32% UK: 17.75% Oceania: 13.28% Canada: 9.52% Rest of the world: 7.25%
Education	PhD: 26.4 % Master degree: 40.5% Bachelor: 26.4% Specific RM certification: 20.2%
Role as RM	Leader: 21% Manager: 41% Operational: 35% Not sure: 3%
Years of experiences as RM	Less than 5 years: 25% 5-9 years: 29% 10-14 years: 20% 15-19 years: 13% More than 20 years: 13%
Other info	Employer University: 87% Research Institute: 6% Other: 7% Public: 77% Private non-profit: 22% For-profit: 1%

Table 7 – Main characteristics of respondents of the 2019 RAAAP survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 75%
Age	Age groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 24 and under: 0.5% - 25-34: 13.6% - 35-44: 36.1% - 45-54: 30.2% - 55-64: 16.2% - 65 and over: 2.2% - Prefer not to provide: 1.2%
Countries	United States of America: 34% Europe (excl. UK): 23% UK: 12% Oceania: 12% Canada: 8% Rest of the world: 11%

Education	PhD: 28% Master degree: 24% Bachelor: 30% Specific RM certification: 24% Knows 2 or more languages: 46%
Role as RM	- Leader: 18% - Manager: 41% - Operational: 38% - Not sure: 3%
Years of experiences as RM	Less than 5 years: 28% 5-9 years: 27% 10-14 years: 22% 15-19 years: 11% More than 20 years: 12%
Other info	Employer University: 83% Research Institute: 8% Other: 9% Public: 78% Private non-profit: 20% For-profit: 2% Not sure: 1% Permanent: 81% Fixed term: 15% Other: 4%

Main results concerning training – 1st edition of the survey

Rating of skills

In the 2016 survey, respondents were asked to rate the importance of hard skills and soft skills needed to perform their job.

Specifically, in the survey the hard skills included:

1. Proposal development
 - Identifying, sorting and dissemination of funding opportunities
 - Preparing proposals for research funding
 - Budget development / costing and pricing of research proposals
2. Project support
 - Drafting, negotiating and accepting contracts and subawards
 - Dealing with project finances / monitoring sponsored project financial activity
 - Employing staff (e.g. researchers or research administrators) on externally funded research projects
 - Reporting to Funders
3. Translation
 - Supporting research impact: facilitating the use of academic research both within academia, and in the wider world
 - Knowledge exchange and business development – helping academic staff to work with industry and other third parties to mutual benefit

- Technology Transfer: where new businesses are created, or businesses explicitly use intellectual property generated from research
- Supporting the delivery of revenue generating short courses, e.g. through budget development
- 4. Supporting post graduate research (PhD)/graduate/doctoral students
- 5. Policy and Governance
 - Contributing to research policy and strategy
 - Supporting internal or external research assessment (e.g. the REF in the UK, ERA in Australia)
 - Supporting research ethics and governance
- 6. Working with research information systems (e.g. MIS, ERA, CRIS)
- 7. Audit and Compliance
 - Supporting audit: including compliance, and internal and external audit support
 - Working with External Auditors / Making statutory returns (e.g. in the US - Uniform Guidance, Subpart F [A133])
- 8. Service Delivery
 - Managing a research support service / office / function
 -

On the other side, the soft skills included:

1. Communication skills: it includes conveying information on policies clearly (verbally and written), report writing, preparing and conducting presentations, and tailoring communications to targeted audiences
2. Teamwork/Collaboration: it includes working closely with central and academic departments, in addition to promoting good teamwork of staff
3. Adaptability/Change Management: it includes identifying external changes early on, and developing strategies for managing change
4. Problem-solving: ability to identify problems and recommend solutions
5. Critical Observation: ability to analyse and summarize aggregated data to various audiences
6. Conflict Resolution: requires negotiation skills and finding peaceful solutions when two or more parties are in disagreement over something
7. Initiative Taking: being a “self-starter”, proactive rather than reactive, persistent in overcoming difficulties that arise in pursuit of a goal
8. Cultural and Diversity skills: being sensitive to diverse cultural perspectives and encouraging teamwork of diverse groups
9. Decision Making: the ability to make good decisions with missing or incomplete information
10. Taking Responsibility: accepting and demonstrating personal responsibility for compliance areas, and for staff
11. Project Management: assigning tasks and managing deadlines for an overall project goal (e.g. implementation of a new system, policy or procedure)
12. Mentoring and Coaching: providing advice and support for others either formally or informally.

Research administrators holding leadership positions assigned high importance to their soft skills, rating them as very or extremely important in more than 90% of the answers. The same skills were rated as very or extremely important only by the 50% of respondents employed at operational level. Additionally, the respondents were asked when the skills that they have indicated as being most important were developed, i.e. if these skills were developed while in the position, through formal training and learning “on the job” or these skills were owned prior to the current position. Only 14% of the participants reported that these skills were developed while in the position.

When comparing the average of ratings of three “Proposal Development” hard skills versus the average of all of the soft skills, the survey showed that leaders and managers reported higher importance of soft skills as compared to the proposal development related hard skills. Whereas Operational roles reported a higher proportion of their hard skills as being more important than their soft skills. Kerridge and Scott (2017)

concluded that those holding leadership positions in research administration give more importance to their soft skills than their professional hard skills.

Main results concerning training – 2nd edition of the survey

In the second survey (2019) the part related to the skills and their rating was omitted, but interesting questions concerning the usefulness of professional accreditations and the importance of alignment of education/experience in the subject area(s) that RMs support were added.

In the 2019 survey, it emerged the importance of having relevant skills for the position, and then further developing those skills and adding new skills after taking on the role. Skills are described to be 360-degree or wide-ranging and they even look like never enough for the role (Poli et al., 2023).

Usefulness of professional accreditation

Respondents were given a list of available professional accreditation related to research management and administration, and then were asked to evaluate those they achieved with respect to their professional relevance. These evaluations were not entirely positive. According to most of them, the professional accreditations did not have any relevance for gaining a promotion/a new job (58%), helping them in their current job (55%), giving them more confidence in their abilities (54%), or increasing their credibility with faculty/academics/researchers (53%). In addition, 42% of the respondents that do not have professional accreditation are skeptical on the usefulness of these accreditation for career progressions. Similar responses were obtained isolating only the European respondents.

Nevertheless, the first RAAAP survey revealed that those in leadership roles are more likely (32%) to hold professional certifications than those in managerial (22.5%) and operational (20.6%) roles. Therefore, there seems to be a link between professional certification and advancement within the RM profession. Kerridge and Scott (2018) have hypothesised that RM specific certifications have helped individuals progress into more senior RM positions.

Importance of alignment with the research areas supported

The respondents were asked if they consider important to have education/experience in the subject area(s) that they support. For example, if it is important to have a background close to natural and life science when supporting research implementation in that area. The minority of the respondents considered as no important the alignment (28%) while the majority gave a lot of importance (30%) or a relatively low importance (38%) to this aspect. This finding suggests that a technical training concerning the subjects of the research which is supporting is important and could justify the transition from the role of researcher to the one of RM in the same field of studies.

The recent paper by Poli et al. (2023) commented on the results of the 2019 RAAAP survey. The paper confirms that a career in RM is rarely an intentional choice, while it is described as “labyrinthine”. Overall, when respondents were asked how they came to work in research administration, less than a fifth made an intentional choice (19.8% of n=4,313), most fell into the position (59.5%), and some were moved into an RM role (9.9%), and the rest for other reasons.

Professional development classes

The respondents were asked if they have taken specific professional development classes (separate from academic courses and professional accreditation) and whether these helped their career or not.

The respondents selected the following specific classes listed in order of percentage of cases.

- Communication skills: 51%
- Project Management: 47%
- Teamwork/Collaboration: 40%
- Cultural and Diversity skills: 38%
- Adaptability/Change Management: 31%
- Conflict Resolution: 30%

- Stress Management: 26%
- Mentoring: 22%
- Problem-Solving: 20%
- Coaching: 20%
- Service Culture: 14%
- Taking Responsibility: 14%
- Other: 14%
- Initiative taking: 13%
- Language Skills: 10%
- Critical Observation: 8%

In the “free comment” space, many respondents gave positive evaluation of the attended professional development classes, which were considered useful for their career advancement.

3.1.3 HETFA survey

Context of the survey

A really insightful analysis was published in 2019 by the HETFA, the Hungarian Research Institute and Center for Economic and Social Analysis (Virágh et al., 2019). The investigation shed light on conditions, skills and competences needed by RMs, with the final goal to get enough knowledge to prepare and implement a proper European educational and research project.

Within this context, HETFA developed and circulated among European RMs an online questionnaire that consisted of 35 questions, covering the topics of demographics, educational and professional background, place of work, advantages and disadvantages of the job, recruitment, skills and competencies and RM-related trainings and associations.

The online questionnaire was made available for distribution between 21st of February and 20th of March 2019. The survey was circulated through the BESTPRAC²² mailing list consisting of 600 recipients being part of the network and/or having attended to any of its events and trainings. In addition, the survey was promoted via Facebook and LinkedIn for professionals.

The questions of the survey are available in the annex of the HETFA discussion paper (Virágh et al., 2019).²³

Survey respondents

The HETFA survey targeted the European RM’s community. 136 respondents filled in the questionnaire, but only 89 completed it fully.

Table 8 furnishes a summary of the main characteristics of the respondents that provided the information of HETFA survey.

Table 8. Main characteristics of respondents of the HETFA survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 72.3%
Age	31-50 years: 81.4%
Countries	Respondents came from 31 different European countries

²² “BESTPRAC: The Voice of Research Administrators - Building a network of administrative excellence” is a European network of research managers that was initially funded by COST programme in 2014, cfr <https://bestprac.eu/home/>

²³ https://hetfa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Research-managers_final_0408.pdf

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 35.6% Eastern countries (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Serbia, and Ukraine) - 33.9% Western countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, the Netherlands, UK and Switzerland) - 23.7% Southern countries (Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal and Spain) - 6.8% Northern countries (Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Latvia and Norway) - No answers from Czech Republic, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Slovakia and Sweden
Education	PhD: 29.7 % PhD and master: 91.6% Specific RM certification: 6%
Role as RM	Manager: 49.1% Advisor: 18.2% Administrator: 14.5% At least 5 years of experience: 77% At least 10 years of experience: 38%
Other info	Country of origin is usually the same as country of work Member of a professional RM Association: 36% Public institute: 68.8% Private non-profit: 27.5% Private profit: 3.7% University: 60.5% Research institute: 24.8%

Main results concerning training

RM's skills and competences

Participants to HETFA questionnaire were asked which skills and behavioural competences were considered necessary to fulfil RM job. Specifically, they rated the following skills:

- analytical skills
- mediation, negotiation
- information management
- information search
- IT skills
- interpersonal skills, networking, influencing
- teamwork
- problem solving
- administrative skills
- initiation
- cultural and diversity skills
- English knowledge.

Similarly, the rating of behavioural competences were among:

- flexibility
- teambuilding, motivation building
- leadership, decision-making
- planning, strategic thinking
- assertiveness
- openness
- creativity

- efficiency
- reliability
- values appreciation
- ethics.

In addition to multitasking and English knowledge, problem solving, teamwork, interpersonal skills and information management were considered of outmost important among the required skills. As for the necessary competences, reliability, efficiency, flexibility and planning, strategic thinking, teambuilding and motivation building were considered as conditions for being a successful RM.

These results are in line with the ones obtained with CARDEA survey.

Moreover, the HETFA report underlined clearly that RM profession needs a wide variety of different skills and competencies. This is proven by the high rates of “rather important” and “very important” answers. Again, this finding are in line with the literature (Tauginiene, 2009).

Difficulties in recruiting and training RMs

The respondents were asked about their experiences in the recruitment of RMs. 61.6% of participants agreed or strongly agreed on the difficulties to recruit colleagues bearing the necessary knowledge and skills and only a minority of respondents (16.3%) experienced a huge number of applications from which they could select the best candidates. In the HETFA report, this phenomenon was justified by the lack of awareness and lack of clear professional profile as well as dedicated undergraduate educational programme, so that many people never identify RM job as an opportunity (Green & Langley, 2009).

In addition, 80.2% of respondents agree or strongly agree on the fact that the training of newcomers is a long process which needs a lot of investment. This shows the strong need for a formal training especially considering the wide variety of skills and knowledge needed for the job and the competitive, uncertain and volatile nature of the work environment. Nevertheless, according to HETFA respondents, many work environments and institutions lack training opportunities for beginners.

Training for RMs

Only 6% of respondents claimed to have a professional accreditation or certification related to RM. The HETFA report clarified that “specific certificate” relates to either project management, international or research and innovation project management or Prince2 project management. 52.9% knows about some kind of program or certificate, these usually being programs offered by national or European ARMA organizations or BESTPRAC.

36% of the respondents is a member of a RMs’ associations and usually use the services of the organization, including for training opportunities, knowledge exchange, study trips to other institutions, workshops, events for networking and other activities.

The respondents were asked what kind of training or education would be useful for becoming a RM (available options were a. short term training - less than 1 month long; b. long term training - less than 1 yearlong; c. vocational educational programme; d. module or educational programme at higher education; e. other postgraduate educational programme). The variety of answers reflected the problematic nature of setting a formal training for an ill-defined and fast changing job. Though some respondents pointed out that any training is better than no training, all in all they seemed to be rather skeptical about training content. Many thought the best way to learn is on-the-job. They felt that the content and length of training initiatives should depend on the educational and professional background of the candidate, as well as the institution they work for. Many felt that success in research management depends more on having the necessary soft skills, which are hard to get in a formal training. Some of the respondents considered formal training either not necessary, or not possible. They saw that the best is to have some kind of scientific background and the necessary soft

skills, while hard skills should rather be picked up on-the-job. They thought what would really be useful is coaching and mentoring from a more experienced colleague.

For formal training, a **problem-oriented hands-on training** with case studies, examples, challenges and their solutions was considered as almost useful. In addition, according to respondents, flexibility was another “must have” for training, that could be achieved by modules, which could be adjusted to the starting knowledge of the participants.

3.1.4 EARMA PDRC survey

Context of the survey

The results of this survey were presented in occasion of the EARMA conference 2022 held in May in Oslo. This survey launched in 2021 was carried out in the context of the EARMA Professional Development and Recognition Committee (PDRC) by an international team of RMs. The PDRC working group is active in monitoring the trends and novelties concerning the thematic of professional development for RMs treated under several aspects of professional accreditation, professional development policy, recognition of RM profession, education and training, system of review, quality assurance and evaluation, continuing professional development (CPD).

The purpose of the survey was to get an overview on training initiatives and needs of the RMs in Europe and beyond, in order to provide inputs for high quality training for RMs and to identify relevant topics, emerging skills and preferred training tools, according to RMs needs. The survey originated from the mapping of existing training initiatives of RMs associations worldwide, carried out by an Italian RMs working group in 2020 (Romano and Albanesi, 2021).

The EARMA PDRC survey consists of 32 questions and is available online²⁴.

Survey respondents

The survey targeted the RM's community. In total, 124 responses were received.

Table 9 furnishes a summary of respondents' demographic profile.

Table 9. Main characteristics of respondents of the HETFA survey

Characteristics	Info
Gender	Female: 79%
Age	Age groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 25-34: 14% - 35-44: 50% - 45-54: 31% - 55-64: 4% - 65 and over: 1%
Countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 36.3% EU Southern countries - 28.2% EU Northern countries - 24.2% EU Western countries - 3.2% EU Eastern countries - 8.1% Rest of world UN Classification for Macro-Regions
Years of experiences as RMs	Newcomer: 4% 0-5 y: 26% 5-9 y: 25% 10-14 y: 32% 15-19 y: 8% +20 y: 5%
Role as RM	Leading: 6% Managing and coordinating: 56% Operational: 36% Other: 2%
Other info	Type of contract

²⁴ <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/TX2VKQ9>

	Permanent: 54% Temporary: 44% Other: 2%
	Employer University: 73% Research Institute: 15% Other: 12%
	Public: 86% Private: 14%

Core results concerning training

The results indicated that RMs were active in participating in training courses. Indeed, 57% of respondents were aware of training courses for RMs in their countries. Most respondents participated in training courses at least once a year (35%), 27% every 3 months and 21% more often. 60% of the institutions of RMs promoted the participation of their personnel in training courses allowing for both training leave and financial support. Training providers were mainly national contact points, consultancy companies and national authorities. In Northern and Western Europe also RM associations were active in training.

Although 1-day trainings were by far the most common option throughout Europe and the world, other ideal training structure were proposed by respondents that indicated as preferred a flexible MOOC-type training with lectures available on-line and flexible assignments' submission, followed by a series of workshops over two years and a week-long intensive training.

The survey also indicated that the most influential factor in RMs' choice of training is its relevance to everyday work and the career advancement.

Most respondents were not aware of available accredited courses in their country. This could be due to scarcity of certified courses, but it underlined the necessity for a more effective circulation of information and the lack of a unique site of reference where to find news and data.

Finally, from the survey it emerged that 40% of respondents were trainer themselves and 25% of which had a certification to act as trainer or teacher.

3.1.5 Other surveys

Other surveys that investigate the training ecosystem for RMs and can potentially provide further insights are the ones listed below:

- [RI:train project surveys](#)²⁵, aimed to identify priority training needs of managers of research infrastructures. The results of this survey were used to develop the RI:train staff/knowledge exchange programme;
- [RI:TRAIN Plus quantitative survey](#)²⁶, targeting specifically top level managers who lead European or national initiatives but also sites (e.g. subnational or national nodes) to define an understanding about what makes Research Infrastructures and their Core Facilities institutions, a success and what is important to their members with diverse backgrounds, tasks, interests and training needs.
- [Professionals at the Interface of Science \(PloS\) survey](#)²⁷, which is part of a wider research project that systematically analyses the context and impact of professionals in research and innovation ecosystems and their self-recognition within the PloS community. The overall aim is to contribute to the research studies concerning research management by providing an analysis of this missing part of the community, namely their identity, professional paths, and community representation (Santos et al., 2021).
- [The foRMAtion project output 1](#)²⁸ which is a report including a survey targeting RMs, university teachers, interested researchers, students at HEIs to identify existing good and bad practices about the current educational and training programs, tools and methods for the empowerment of potential RMs, as well as to identify the conditions, skills and competences potential RMs need to acquire for the drafting and implementation of excellent EU projects.
- [The RM ROADMAP project's survey](#)²⁹ was launch in November 2023 and collected over 1700 complete responses from Europe, whose results were available in summer 2024. This RM Roadmap survey aimed to gather a comprehensive picture of the current situation of RMs across Europe, to get insight on key skills, attitudes and behaviors of successful RMs, their involvement in support for impact, and their routes into the profession.

²⁵ <https://www.esfri.eu/project-landmarks-news/ritrain-surveys-training-needs-managers-ris>

²⁶ <https://data.aussda.at/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.11587/RBXAZ7>

²⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/survey-rmas-agencies/home>

²⁸ <https://www.formation-rma.eu/results/>

²⁹ https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/RM_ROADMAP_survey_dataset/26503675

3.1.6 Main findings from the surveys

The main features of the training ecosystem for RMs, as depicted by the analyzed surveys, could be summarized as follows:

- **RMs need vast range of skills.** When CARDEA and HETFA surveys' respondents were asked to rate the importance of a range of skills, they rated as "rather important" and "very important" the majority of the listed skills and the high frequency of these answers show that RM profession needs a wide variety of different skills and competencies. Similar results were reported in the RAAAP survey and this is confirmed also from the scientific literature. Indeed, all contributions agree on the fact that RMs need to have a vast range of skills and knowledge. According to Shambrook and Roberts (2011) a dedicated successful RM has to be multi-talented and mission-oriented. The most significant contributions dealing with the definition of RMs, their main professional roles and professional frameworks are included in the reference list.
- **Importance recognized to soft skills.** In the CARDEA survey, it emerged that transversal skills are the ones perceived as most important and crucial for daily research management work. However, albeit they are perceived as most important, **few training opportunities on soft skills are available.** In the first RAAAP survey (2016), RMs in leadership positions assigned high importance to their soft skills, rating them as very or extremely important in more than 90% of cases. In the same survey, the same skills were rated as very or extremely important only by 50% of respondents employed at operational level. The conclusion was that RMs in leadership positions place more importance on their soft skills than their professional hard skills. Similar results emerged in the HETFA survey, in which many of the respondents felt that success in research management depends more on having the necessary soft skills that are hard to get via formal training. Some of the respondents considered formal training either not necessary, or not possible. They saw that the best is to have some kind of scientific background and the necessary soft skills, while hard skills should rather be picked up on-the-job.
- **Lack of training opportunities for RMs.** In the CARDEA survey, 81% of respondents did not have any specific research management qualifications or certifications, 45.8% of respondents had no professional development plan at all, 41.6% have not engaged in CPD in the last year and, among those that have engaged in CPD, 22.6% have engaged in learning on their personal time. Similarly, the HETFA report underlines the lack of specific educational programs, which is reflected in the **difficulties to recruit RMs** bearing the necessary knowledge and skills. In addition, training of newcomers is recognized as a long process which needs a lot of investment. In the HETFA survey, only 6% of respondents claimed to have any kind of professional accreditation or certification related to RM.
- Training should be **relevant to daily work tasks** and should have a **problem-oriented and hands-on approach** with case studies, examples about possible challenges and their solutions. In the EARMA survey, ideal training structure were proposed by respondents that indicated a preference for a flexible MOOC-type training with lectures available on-line and flexible assignments' submission. Other preferred training options were a series of workshops over two years and a week-long intensive training. The EARMA survey also indicated that the relevance to everyday work tasks and career advancement is the most influential factor in RMs' choice of training. In the HETFA survey, respondents indicated that **coaching and mentoring from a more experienced colleague** is extremely useful. As for formal training, a problem-oriented hands-on training with case studies, examples, challenges and their solutions was considered as the most useful. Additionally, according to respondents, **flexibility** is another "must-have" for training. This can be achieved via modules that can be tailored to the background knowledge of the participants.

3.2 Training opportunities for Research Managers

This section gathers and outlines the main training opportunities available to RMs, with information collected in spring 2023. This preliminary desk research helped CARDEA (a) map the research management training ecosystem; (b) understand its functioning; (c) devise and develop new and innovative training modules; and (d) add value to what is available by circulating information and increasing accessibility. In regard to project outputs, CARDEA and its sister project RM ROADMAP³⁰ agreed on creating a unified online dashboard. The dashboard, available in the CARDEA website³¹, offers training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities targeting RMs, increasing the searchability of and the accessibility to reliable and up-to-date information. It was agreed that RM ROADMAP completed an extensive and systematic desk-based research on training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities available to RMs in the ERA and that the results of this research were included in the CARDEA's online dashboard.

This section offers a brief and preliminary summary of the most relevant training opportunities available to RMs. The selection includes certified training opportunities linked to RM professional qualification and other relevant training options.

3.2.1 Certified training for Research Managers

Table 10 collects the most relevant certified training opportunities targeting RMs and offered by RM organizations across the world. In most of cases, the certification is linked to a professional qualification stage (i.e. basic, advanced, or senior level).

Table 10. Main certified training opportunities targeting RMs and offered by RM organizations across the world

Organization	Training Title	Brief Description	Website
EARMA European Association of Research Managers and Administrators	European Certificate in Research Management (CRM)	Training program targeted for RMs with at least 3-4 years' experience. It consists of 5 mandatory units as one-day physical workshops + 1 optional unit on line for a total of about 180 hours of study and submission of written assignments. Upon successful participation, a certificate and 20 ECTS are awarded. Beside CRM, other 2 professional development programmes are offered by EARMA: Early Stage Research Administrators Masterclass (designed for people who have recently moved into research support, 0-4 years' experience. 2 full days (in-person) or 5 half days (online) and Leaders in Research Management .	Link
ARMA Association of Research Managers and Administrators (UK)	Certificate in Research Management: Foundation	The training is an introduction to the research management profession open exclusively to ARMA members and sister associations. The format is a mixture of workshops and webinars, for a total qualification time of 240 h.	Link to factsheet
	Certificate in Research Management: Advanced	The training is for who have experience in research management, and specific responsibilities within their department or unit. The format is a mixture of workshops and webinars, for a total qualification time of 240 h.	Link to factsheet
PRAXIL AURIL UK's professional association for Knowledge Exchange practitioners	Registered Technology Transfer Professional (RTTP)	RTTP is the international professional standard for knowledge transfer and commercialisation practitioners working in universities, industry and government labs. To earn RTTP, it is necessary to demonstrate the core competencies needed to work effectively in the profession and an established track record including for RTTP training courses.	Link
	Candidate RTTP	Candidate RTTP is a designation that allows entrants to the profession to signal that they have committed to a pathway of training and development leading to the award of full RTTP status. It indicates to employers that they are serious about their career and aspire to meet the highest standards.	

³⁰ <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/>

³¹ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/dashboard/>

Organization	Training Title	Brief Description	Website
SRA INTERNATIONAL Society of Research Administrators International	LevelUP Micro-credential Program	The program consists of training modules that are 2 to 5 hours in duration on topics most relevant to research administration professional. For each module completed, the students earn a micro-credential and a digital badge, thought 5 levels.	Link
	Certificate Programs	The SRAI Certificate Program offers comprehensive training in the field of research administration & management through 10 certificates. Each certificate includes a required half-day or full-day workshop and a specific amount of required and elective concurrent sessions.	Link
	Continuing Education Units (CEU)	Continuing Education Unit (CEU) is a recognized measure of participation in a continuing education program. A CEU is defined as 1 CEU per hour. Registrants will receive continuing education units and credit for all modules and plenaries they attend during the meeting.	Link
CARA – ACAAR The Canadian Association of Research Administrators	Research Management and Coordination Certificate	The program prepares graduates to move into positions of leadership within the field of research administration. The format is flexible, with fully-online program delivery. All students will have the opportunity to identify a Professional Mentor through the CARA-ACAAR or their own networks. The program is held in collaboration with the Canadian Mohawk College	Link
	Research Administration Certificate	The program is aimed at pre-management research administrators or those planning a career in research administration. Cover core components of research administration. Led by industry professionals, courses are offered in a flexible, part-time, online and interactive format that may include face-to-face live video conferencing. The program is held in collaboration with the Canadian Mohawk College	Link
ARMS Australasian Research Management Society (Singapore, Australia, New Zealand)	Foundation Level Accreditation Program (FLAP)	ARMS accredits the 3 levels with its own scale: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25 points FLAP for new to research management/administration with less than 5 years experience; • 100 points ELAP for mid to senior Research Management Professionals who wish to enhance their leadership, management, and content skills; • 150 points ALAP for who are knowledgeable in their research management role and skilled in applying research management principles in their workplace. The programs comprise of a mix of taught material, group discussions and written assignments.	Link
	Established Level Accreditation Program (ELAP)		Link
	Advanced Level Accreditation Program (ALAP)		Link
RACC Research Administrators Certification Council	Certified Research Administrator (CRA®)	The RACC is a private, independent, nonprofit organization that develops and administers a voluntary program for the certification of individuals who meet the requirements established by RACC. RACC certifies that an individual, through experience and testing, has the fundamental knowledge necessary to be a professional research or sponsored programs administrator.	Link
	Certified Pre-Award Research Administrator (CPRA®)		Link
	Certified Financial Research Administrator (CFRA)		Link

Other RM professional associations and networks listed below - not exhaustive list - offer training programs for RMs, in some cases differentiated by the level of experience of the participants, albeit not linked to professional qualifications or certifications:

- [ARMA-NL](#), The Association for Research Managers and Administrators in the Netherlands
- [DARMA](#), Danish Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [FORTRAMA](#), German Research and Transfer Management Network
- [Finn-ARMA Network](#), Finnish Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [NARMA](#), Norwegian Network for Administration and Research Management
- [BE-ARMA](#), Belgian Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [CZARMA](#), Czech Association of Research Managers and Administrators

- [ICEARMA](#), Icelandic Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [Italian Research Managers](#) network
- [PIC](#), Plataforma de Interface à Ciência
- [RMAN-J](#), The Research Manager and Administrator Network Japan
- [BRAMA](#), Brazilian Association of Research Managers and Administrators
- [WARIMA](#), West African Research and Innovation Management Association
- [V4+WB](#) Network of Research Managers and Administrators from Visegrad Four (V4) and Western Balkan (WB) countries
- [INORMS](#), International Network of Research Management Societies

It must be noted that the Southern African Research & Innovation Management Association (SARIMA)³² offers training opportunities for RMs. Moreover, SARIMA has developed a professional recognition framework structured in 3 levels: Research Administration Professional (RAP) for new comers with 0-3 years of experience; Research Management Professional (RMP) for RMs at intermediate level with 3-5 years of experience; and Senior Research Management Professional (SRMP) for experts with more than 5 years of experience. Recognition in this framework is not strictly linked to the attendance of training. The professional recognition is entrusted by the International Professional Recognition Council (IPRC) which is an autonomous body composed by peers through the review of a portfolio of evidence, which includes prior learning, experience, functional and transferable expertise. The professional designation is valid for five years, after which it should be renewed or upgraded.

3.2.2 EU and international training projects and initiatives for Research Managers

The list below collects interesting training initiatives for RMs. Albeit some of these projects are over, the educational materials could be easily retrieved and used.

- [EUPM2](#) - A new academic path for EU Project managers: narrowing the gaps to enable better project design and management in Europe. Erasmus+ project: 1/12/2021-30/11/2024.
- [PATTERN](#) Empowering Open and Responsible Research and Innovation. HORIZON Europe project, call WIDERA 2022-ERA-01-44.
- [TrainRDM](#) - Open Science and Research Data Management Innovative and Distributed Training Programme. Erasmus+ project: 1/11/2020-30/4/2023.
- [RECAPHE](#) - Enhancing Staff Research and Innovation Capacity in Professional Higher Education. Erasmus+ project: 1/9/2019-31/12/2022.
- [OBERRED](#) - Open Badge Ecosystem for the Recognition of skills in Research Data management and sharing. Erasmus+ project: 1/9/2019-31/8/2022.
- [foRMAtion](#) - Innovative and smart module FO for potential Research Managers and Administrators in higher education. Erasmus+ project: 1/9/2019-31/12/2022. As follow-up activities, the foRMAtion has launched two initiatives – [Alliance on the RMA Educational Module for RMA teachers and the Alliance on the Mentorship Programme for RMA mentors](#)
- [V4+WB](#) project - Network of Research Managers and Administrators from Visegrad Four (V4) and Western Balkan (WB) countries to contribute to their more successful participation in the EU R&I programmes
- [BESTPRAC](#) – COST project which is a targeted network that gathers administrative, financial and legal staff at universities and research-driven institutions who support transnational external competition based (in particular EU funded) research projects.
- [FORTHEM](#) European University Alliance that offers a series of workshops under the framework title “Professional Research Management in Multicultural Exchange”
- [Rltrain](#) - Tailored training for managers in research infrastructures project (2015-2020) developed a two-year European Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures (EMMRI) programme. H2020 EXCELLENT SCIENCE - Research Infrastructures

³² <https://www.sarima.co.za/>

- [RITrainPlus](#) - Research infrastructure training plus aims at designing and delivering short-cycle Continuous Professional Development courses (CPDs) for current and potential leaders in RIs and to establish a permanent European School for Management of Research Infrastructures. H2020 EXCELLENT SCIENCE - Research Infrastructures

On the CARDEA website³³, there are available training materials targeting RMs.

Other EU relevant projects are:

- [OpenInno Train](#) - Research Translation and Applied Knowledge Exchange in Practice through University-Industry-Cooperation. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/1/2019-30/6/2024.
- [RISE BPM](#) - Propelling Business Process Management by Research and Innovation Staff Exchange. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/5/2015-30/4/2019.
- [EM4FIT](#) - Entrepreneurial Management for Fostering Innovation and Talents. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/1/2020-31/12/2023.
- [BeingL S](#) - Meeting the challenges of delivering projects successfully in the 21st century. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/1/2017-30/9/2022.
- [HEIM](#) - Higher Education Internationalization and Mobility: Inclusion, Equalities and Innovations. H2020-RISE MSCA project, 1/1/2015-31/12/2017.

3.2.3 Main academic training for Research Managers

As reported in the HETFA Discussion Paper (2019), the existing programs available are for post-graduates or for professionals already working in the field, whereas apart from the Anglo-Saxon world, there is a huge lack of the educational programs of RMs. The following list, albeit not exhaustive, gives an idea of the vast possibilities of academic paths for RMs in the Anglo-Saxon world, while it underlines the need of training for RMs in the European context.

Some universities, mainly in US, offer training paths preparing for the job of research management. The list below, not exhaustive, offers an overview of some available academic trainings for RMs:

- [European Research and Transfer Management \(EURESTMA\) certificate](#), organized by an alliance of European academic providers
- [European Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures \(EMMRI\)](#) programme implemented at University of Milano Bicocca and developed within the H2020 project [Rltrain](#) - Tailored training for managers in research infrastructures project (2015-2020)
- [MS in Research Administration](#), Johns Hopkins University
- [Research administration](#), University of Maryland
- [Master of Science in Research Administration and Compliance](#), New York School of Professional Studies
- [Master of Science in Research Administration](#), “Emmanuel College” in Boston Harvard
- [Master of research administration](#), University of Central Florida
- [Researcher Management and Leadership Training](#), University of Colorado
- [Research Administration program](#), University of Montana
- [Research Administration](#), Rush University
- [Graduate Certificate in Research Administration](#), Central Michigan University
- [Professional Certificate \(PCert\) Research Management](#), Cambridge Centre for Innovation and Development

³³ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/cardeaacademy/>

3.3 Breaking the barriers: Research Managers' skills based on the perspective of the "others"

The surveys analysed and presented in paragraph 3.1 were all targeting RMs, so the respondents to the surveys' questions were all RMs. This circumstance may lead to generate results that are auto-referential, i.e. that do not take into account needs and expectations of all the other key actors of research and innovation ecosystems: researchers to be supported, research institutions and universities, policy makers and other stakeholders.

In order to enhance the quality of the services provided by RMs, investigating what the above-mentioned target groups expect from RMs (i.e. what skills RMs should have in order to fulfil their role) was seen as key and strategic. The following sections present the investigation carried out to gather information on the perception of research management and RMs by (a) policy makers in the field of research and innovation; (b) institutions and organisations hiring RMs; and (c) opinion leaders.

3.3.1 The perspective of policy makers

This investigation has started in 2022 within CARDEA consortium that has collected the main policy documents that were mentioning the professional figure of RM at the European level and at national level for the Member States represented by the countries of the CARDEA partners (i.e. Ireland, Italy, Poland, Spain, Greece, Croatia, Belgium and Romania). The main CARDEA results are available in this deliverable. In 2023 this collection was continued by RM ROADMAP that, thanks to the network of the RM National Ambassadors, collected the main policy documents mentioning the professional figure of RMs per each European country. The result of this investigation is reported in one of their consensus document³⁴.

In order to have a complete overview of the perception of research management, CARDEA strategically analysed policy documents available in 2022 and beginning of 2023, at EU and national level that contain mentions, definitions or other descriptors of RMs and their profession. This analysis provides useful insights on what policy makers expect RMs to do, what skills they think RMs need and, consequently, what training is necessary.

EU documents

The first analysed document is the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2021-2022, with particular emphasis on the WIDERA section³⁵. In the introduction, when speaking of the "brain circulation" phenomenon, there is specific mention to "research managers" that are at the service of the ERA. Additionally, in the description of the Twinning actions, in order to raise the research profile of an institution from a Widening country, special focus should be dedicated to the strengthening of research management, as this is considered of primary importance. In the ERA Talents call, in which secondments are open also to other research and innovation talents – such as administrative, managerial and technical staff supporting R&I activities into organizations, there is a description of "*other research and innovation talents' in R&I support capacity, such as knowledge brokers, data stewards, research managers, research infrastructure operators, knowledge and technology transfer officers, etc.*".

In the same document, under the description of call ERA-01-20 (the same call that funded CARDEA and RM ROADMAP projects), it is reported that "*research management can take many shapes: research policy advisers, research managers, financial support staff, data stewards, research infrastructure operators, knowledge transfer officers, business developers, knowledge brokers, innovation managers, etc. Entities and regions who are proven strong and excellent hubs in knowledge creation and innovation usually rely on a*

³⁴ <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/co-creation-results>

³⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf

strong population of research managers.”. The same wording is present in ERA policy AGENDA of November 2021.

In the following Horizon Europe Work Programme 2022-2023 WIDERA part³⁶, under the description of call 2024 ERA-01-03, the previous definition of research management was enriched with a revised list of roles: “the research management takes various shapes across the ERA (and beyond), and therefore its definition/scope is multi-dimensional, including but not limited to the following roles: research policy advice, evidence-based policy making, foresight and strategy development; research coordination, research development, research project and funding management, financial support; evaluation and assessment support; research and complementary training programme management; data-based research support, such as data stewards and data analysts, exploitation of research data, data protection; specialised research infrastructure operation; scientific integrity and ethics expertise, gender perspective support, legal support; science communication support; knowledge transfer and innovation support, knowledge brokering, incubator coordination and business development. In particular, the aim of this action is to further develop and implement a methodology to identify, train and 'professionalise' individuals who are essential support for the 'research enterprise'.”.

Moreover, the Work Programme 2023-2024 recognises the strategic role of RMs in the research and innovation ecosystems, reporting that the “research performing and funding entities, local ecosystems, and regions that are strong in knowledge creation and circulation usually rely on a strong community of RMs, while lower R&I intense countries, regions, institutions often lack such communities, or do not have sufficient access to expertise.”

Finally, albeit it is not a policy document, it is worth mentioning the ESCO (The European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations) website³⁷, which describes and classifies professional occupations and skills relevant to the EU labour market and education and training, providing descriptions of over 3,000 occupations and 13,800 skills. In this website, there are definitions of these professional figures: research managers, research and development managers, grants management officers, public funding advisors, EU funds managers, policy officers, intellectual property consultants, data analysts, data scientist. On the other side, there are no definition of data steward, research infrastructure operators, technology transfer/knowledge valorisation officer (info retrieved on April 2023).

European national documents

Our next step was to use the CARDEA consortium as a pilot pool of resources for national policies. Specifically, each CARDEA partner was asked to collect its own national documents that were relevant to this purpose. Table 11 summarizes the findings of this preliminary investigation.

Table 11. National documents that contain mentions, definitions or other items of descriptions that can depict the professional figure of RMs.

Country	Documents	Notes/definition of Research Managers
Ireland	Irish University Association Researcher Career Development Framework	The document reports that the research ecosystem includes researchers complemented by research support roles defined as “Research Officer” and “Research Assistant” (Page 17)
	Science Foundation Ireland's (SFI) Research Centres Programme	The programme includes provisions for funding of research management and research assistant personnel, named as project manager, IP manager, Education & Public Engagement Manager (Page 11)
	Irish National Research Policy	The document recognizes the importance of impact of talents for R&I ecosystem, but there is no explicit mention to RMs (Page 3)

³⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023-2024/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf

³⁷ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

Italy	National Research Plan 2021-2027	Concerning the new emerging professional figure of RM, the documents reports the following statements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>"Research Managers" will have to be the glue between the training systems at all levels, research, businesses and of the institutions, to promote and accompany the twin transitions, digital and green...</i> (Page 29) • <i>The new generation of Research Managers will also have to accompany the transition to an open science and open innovation approach...</i> (Page 30) • <i>highly qualified Research Managers, who understand the languages of both worlds, that of science and that of business...</i> (Page 30) • <i>the training and recruitment of new professional figures to support research, for example, staff scientists, data managers, data analysts, facility managers and knowledge exchange managers...</i> (Page 42)
	National call for empowerment and capacity building of technology transfer offices 2022	The call foresees a new professional figure, named Innovation Promoter, which will have to play a linking role between the world of academic research and the world of industry. The Innovation Promoter has to act as an enhancer of patent titles towards companies potentially interested in developing and marketing innovations.
	National Recovery and Resilience Plan	The calls foresee the possibility to hire RMs for research projects, and the obligation to hire a infrastructures RM in the case of calls funding research infrastructures.
Poland	Public Employment Services Portal	In the governmental website, there are job posts for foreigners looking for working in Poland. Among other professions, the EU project coordinator is defined as <i>"the responsible for planning, managing and implementing the project, including timely achievement of planned results and settling the budget in accordance with the project assumptions. The coordinator organizes the work of project teams and is responsible for achieving the assumed goals of the project, coordinates and supervises the implementation of EU projects."</i>
Spain	Catalan Law of Science	In this document at Title III, Article 15, people in the service of science are defined as <i>"those workers who contributes to the research and innovation processes and to the maintenance and organisation of the spaces and instruments necessary for this task."</i>
Romania	International standard classification of occupations (ISCO-08)	Under code 1223 of the national classification of occupations the item "managers for research and development" is declined as "branch director for research and design", "head of a research and design project", "head of department for research and design", "head of workshop for research and design", "project director", "head of project/program".
	National Strategy for Research, Innovation and Smart Specialization 2022-2027	The document, that creates the premises and plans for the Romanian future of the research activities, mentions the professional figure of RMs/director. This strategy was transformed into a government law (HG nr. 933/2022)

Some of the CARDEA partners were not aware of specific national policy documents having these characteristics. Namely, at the first semester of 2023, the Greek and Croatian partners reported that such documents do not exist in their countries.

CARDEA survey

The CARDEA survey included a question asking if RM, as a profession, is a defined job title and role in the country of respondents, i.e. if RM professional figure is recognised by legislation or funded explicitly by research funders.

As reported in table 12, just over half of respondents ($n = 243$, 50.3%) indicated that research management as a profession is not a defined role in their countries e.g., is not recognised by the national legislation or funded explicitly by research funders. Only 25 participants (5.3%) indicated that 'yes' research management is a defined job title recognised by legislation or explicitly funded. The remaining responses were 'somewhat' 24% ($n = 116$), 'I don't know' 18.8% ($n = 91$) or 'other' (1.7%, $n = 8$), with one participant indicating research management as a profession was recognised "during early 2010s but in a last couple of years this diminished"; and another revealing that RMs are "in some cases funded by research funders (depends on the content of the job)".

Table 12. Responses to the question about whether research management is recognised as a profession at the national level. Data are separated by the membership of the EU, other European countries and responses from the rest of the world.

	Overall		EU		Europe not EU		Rest of world	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Yes	25	5.2	20	4.6	2	7.4	3	18.8
Somewhat	114	23.7	105	24.2	7	25.9	2	12.5
No	243	50.5	219	50.6	12	44.4	9	56.3
I don't know	91	18.9	83	19.2	5	18.5	2	12.5
Other	8	1.7	6	1.4	1	3.7	0	0.0

Conclusions

As the CARDEA survey highlighted, in the majority of cases, research management is not recognised as a profession by the national legislation nor funded explicitly by research funders.

However, the analysis of recent policy documents initiated by CARDEA reveals that RM are not so "invisible" as they used to be.

The European Union relies on RMs as key actors contributing to the excellence of the research and innovation process in EU (see Action 17 of ERA policy agenda). Moreover, in the WIDERA work programme, it is explicitly reported that entities who are strong in research performance rely on a strong community of RMs, while lower R&I intense countries, regions, institutions often lack such communities. Moreover, in ERA Talent call, secondments are open also to administrative, managerial and technical staff supporting R&I activities. The EU documents report a long list of various shapes of research management across the ERA ranging from research policy adviser to data analysts, specialized research infrastructure operator, scientific integrity and ethics expert... to cite some of them.

At national level, the preliminary analysis conducted by CARDEA revealed that RMs are seen by policy makers as figures that connect the dots of the worlds of science and of business. The RM are seen as the one that have to promote and support the twin transitions, digital and green and the ones who have to accompany the transition to an open science and open innovation approach (Italy). In the Polish, Romanian and Catalan documents RMs are seen as the organizers of the resources, often linked to the realisation of projects (both physical such infrastructures, and human resources).

3.3.2 The perspective of Research Managers' employers

Context

The second step in describing the training ecosystem for RMs from an external perspective was to investigate what skills institutions and organisations expect RMs to have at the recruitment stage.

The surveys analysed in the previous section revealed how challenging the recruitment process for RMs can be. Specifically, in the HETFA survey³⁸, respondents were asked about their experiences in recruiting RMs. Of these, 61.6% agreed or strongly agreed that it was difficult to find candidates with the necessary knowledge and skills. Only a minority of respondents (16.3%) reported receiving a large number of applications from which they could select the best candidates. Furthermore, in the same survey, 80.2% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that training newcomers is a long process requiring substantial investment. Within this context, CARDEA decided to launch a survey targeting employers of RMs.

Methodology

This analysis, focusing on RMs' recruitment, was inspired by the CEDEFOP³⁹ guidelines. CEDEFOP, the European Union's reference center for vocational education and training, aims to support the development of European vocational education and training policies and to contribute to their implementation. According to their approach, gathering intelligence on current and future skill needs within dynamic and complex labor markets supports better matching of training and jobs. Anticipation and matching approaches can help develop tailored training for specific skills in response to labor market needs. Among the methodologies proposed by CEDEFOP to forecast current and future skills needed by the job market, a leading strategy is the launch of "skills surveys" targeting employers. These skills surveys are particularly valuable for education and training providers (public or private) as they provide updated information on skills demand and thus support the design of training programs.

Following the indications present in the CEDEFOP "User guide to developing an employer survey on skill needs"⁴⁰, CARDEA strategically developed a survey targeting employers of RMs.

The CARDEA consortium disseminated the survey among its contacts. However, instead of a mass mailing to all RMs, we preferred to request our contacts to forward the survey to those responsible for RM recruitment within their institutions, including HR office staff. We sent this request to our national RM networks, the RM ROADMAP ambassadors, WIDERA NCPs, and personal contacts. Our goal was to achieve coverage at the EU level, ensuring representation from all Member States.

The survey was built with Microsoft FORMS and was open for approximately two months, from December 2023 until February 2024.

The survey was intentionally concise, with about 30 questions in total, to avoid overburdening RMs, who had already received many surveys in previous months.

Some questions were identical to those in previous surveys (e.g., the initial CARDEA survey) to compare the results from RMs' employers with results from other target groups.

The questionnaire comprised three main sections:

- Section 1: Information on the organization and respondent;
- Section 2: Questions about the selection process of RMs;
- Section 3: Questions about workforce development.

Results

Section 1: Information on the organization and respondent

The first section of the survey aimed to provide an overview of the respondents' identities, their countries of work, professional levels, and the types and sizes of the institutions they work for.

³⁸ https://hetfa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Research-managers_final_0408.pdf

³⁹ <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en>

⁴⁰ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a53db437-3428-11e7-9412-01aa75ed71a1/language-en;doi:10.2816/413514>

Survey Participation and Geographic Coverage

A total of 125 respondents answered the survey, achieving geographical coverage of the entire EU, with all 27 Member States represented (Figure 1).

Professional Levels and Experience

Respondents were asked about their experience levels, which ranged from first-stage RMs (with less than 2 years of experience) to intermediate and advanced levels, up to the expert level. An "other" option was included to capture categories that do not define themselves as RMs but are involved in RM recruitment (e.g. HR office staff). The distribution of respondents (Figure 2) was as follows:

- 60% were senior RMs,
- 18% were established RMs,
- 12% were recognized RMs,
- 7% were first-stage RMs,
- 2% fell into the "other" category.

These results suggest that senior RMs are often involved in the selection and recruitment processes of less experienced or new colleagues.

Types of Institutions

The respondents worked in research institutions, with 76% from public entities and 18% from private entities. The remaining 6% of cases had residual characteristics (Figure 3).

Size of Institutions

According to the number of unit staff employed in the institutions, they were classified into three size categories:

- Small: Less than 100 staff,
- Medium: Between 100 and 999 staff,
- Large: Over 1000 staff.

This classification included both researchers (academic staff) and non-researchers (non-academic staff). Around half of the respondents' institutions were of medium size, considering both academic and non-academic staff (Figure 4).

Overall, these results provide a comprehensive view of the respondents' backgrounds and the institutions they represent, offering valuable context for interpreting the survey findings.

Figure 1 – Working countries of the survey's responders

Figure 2 – Respondents' answers on their career levels

Figure 3 – Institutions of survey's respondents

Figure 4 – Size of the institutions of survey's respondents

Section 2: Questions about the selection process of RMs

The second section of the questionnaire aimed to gain insights into the recruitment process, the difficulties encountered, and the solutions applied. These questions were specific to respondents who indicated that their institutions had hired or attempted to hire a RM in the past 24 months, which accounted for almost 80% of the respondents (Figure 5).

Recruitment Challenges

Among these respondents, almost 70% reported difficulties in finding appealing candidates for the RM positions (Figure 6). Those who encountered such difficulties were asked to select from a list of options the types of problems they faced (Figure 7). The two most common issues were:

- "There were no or few applicants" (69%),
- "Applicants lacked the required work experience" (66%).

Other issues included:

- "Applicants expected wages higher than we can offer" (48%),
- "Applicants lacked required technical skills" (42%),
- "Applicants lacked required qualification/educational level" (34%),
- "Applicants lacked required core/soft skills" (22%),
- "Applicants did not like working conditions we can currently offer" (18%).

Missing Skills in RM Candidates

To identify the specific skills lacking in RM candidates, respondents selected from nine skill families (Table 1) listed in the initial CARDEA survey⁴¹ (Figure 8). The most frequently cited missing skills were:

- "Specialized knowledge for research performing organizational contexts" (87%),
- "Relationship Management" (74%),
- "Project Management" (65%).

The least cited missing skills were:

- "Line management of others (Talent Development)" (20%),
- "Outreach and Community" (26%),
- "Communication" (31%).

Importance of Accredited Qualifications

Respondents were asked if having an accredited qualification related to research management was considered during the recruitment process. Responses were split evenly, with half indicating it had some importance and the other half indicating it was not important (Figure 9). Some textual responses clarified that although accredited qualifications were valued, they were rarely seen among candidates, as it is not common for RM candidates to already have professional certifications. In the initial CARDEA survey²⁵, 81.0% ($n = 460$) of respondents declared do not have any specific research management qualifications or certifications.

Training for Newly Hired RMs

The final two questions of section two focused on the training provided to newly hired RMs. Training content provided included:

- Transversal skills (26%).
- Specific content related to assigned tasks (23%).
- An overview of the main aspects of the RM profession (16%).

⁴¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7882908>

Additionally, 28% of respondents indicated they provide all the proposed training content, while almost half do not rely on any of the proposed options (Figure 10). This suggests a preference for a hands-on approach, learning by doing, and mentoring from more experienced colleagues.

This hypothesis is supported by responses indicating that training for newly hired RMs is primarily conducted by internal RM colleagues or by internal RM colleagues supported by external experts. Only 3% of cases relied solely on external RM experts for training (Figure 11).

Overall, these findings highlight the challenges in recruiting qualified RMs, the specific skills gaps identified, and the prevalent training practices within the institutions surveyed.

Figure 5 – Percentage of respondents’ institutions that in the last 24 months have hired or tried to hire a Research Manager

Figure 6 - Percentage of respondents’ institutions that had difficulties in finding appealing RM candidates

Figure 7 – Specification of typology of problems encountered by respondents’ institutions in finding appealing RM candidates

Table 1 – Skill family as reported in the [initial CARDEA survey](#)⁴²

CARDEA Skill family	Skill description
Technical skills, e.g., subject matter expertise	Data collection and collation, and analysis; discipline-specific skills; IT skills; knowledge of the research systems; language skills; legal skills; understanding and using research evidence.
Specialised knowledge for research performing organisational contexts	Finding funding; lobbying managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism); open access scholarship; organisational behaviour; EU policy drivers; preparation of bids (interinstitutional); preparing funding applications; tech transfer/patents; understanding the funding ecosystem; understanding unconscious bias; HR research.
Project Management	Achieving project deliverables; designing monitoring and evaluation frameworks and indicators; establishing project plans or policies; general project management; knowledge of databases; knowledge of Microsoft projects (or other PM software); meeting management; relationship management; time management.
Outreach and Community	Academic and community relationship support; business and commercial liaison; community and/or public outreach; provision of training; responsibility for engaging with key stakeholders.
Line management of others (Talent Development)	Coaching skills for managers; delivering coaching/mentoring; mentoring; people management and managing team performance; recruitment and selection; reporting or evaluation taking account of differing needs of target audiences; Staff review, performance and development.
Financing/contracting/compliance	Audit trails, reporting on finance to funders or management; conducting due diligence on partners/collaborators; contract negotiation; developing budgets; ensuring adherence to funders' terms and conditions; financial management; monitoring budget, tracking expenditure or cashflow forecasting; navigating funding responsibilities; processing financial claims and payments; procurement.
Communication	Building and maintaining relationships with funders, partners or other stakeholders; coordination of communication; designing and implementing communication plans; media liaison; preparing and writing reports

⁴² <https://zenodo.org/records/7882908>

	(including evaluation reports and funder reports); preparing briefings; presentation skills; public speaking/presentation; social media; website planning and design.
Relationship Management	Building trust within partnerships; collaborating for success; contributing to fair working environments, e.g. anti-bullying initiatives; diplomacy and negotiation, and mediation; facilitation skills; handling difficult conversations; managing competing demands; networking; promoting or supporting mutual learning; teamwork.
Transversal skills	Attention to detail; autonomy creativity; critical thinking; cultural sensitivity; decision making; diversified knowledge set; efficiency; flexibility; leadership; motivation; openness; proactivity; problem-solving; reliability; research integrity/ethical behaviour; strategic thinking; stress management; values appreciation.

Figure 8 – Specification of typology of skills missing in candidates applying for RM positions

Figure 9 – Percentage of employers that takes into consideration the possession of accredited qualifications related to research management

Figure 10 – Typology of training content offered by institutions to the new hired RMs at the first experience

Figure 11 – Typology of trainers for training possibilities offered by institutions to the new hired RMs at the first experience

Section 3: Questions about workforce development

The third section of the questionnaire aimed to understand the context, support, and training offered to the RM workforce once employed at the institution.

Perception of Proficiency Levels

The first question sought to gauge the perception of the proficiency level of colleagues once they are employed. Despite the need for continuous updating in this profession, respondents generally viewed their colleagues as proficient (Figure 12):

- "All" proficient: 25%,
- "Nearly all" proficient: 28%,
- "Over half" proficient: 23%,
- "Some" proficient: 15%,
- "Very few" proficient: 5%.

Missing Skills in Recruited RMs

For those not fully proficient, respondents identified the primary missing skills (Figure 13) as:

- "Specialized knowledge for research performing organizational contexts" (73%),
- "Relationship management" (61%).

Less frequently missing skills were:

- "Communication" (28%),
- "Outreach and community" (29%),
- "Line management of others (talent development)" (29%).

The prevalent missing skills align with those identified during recruitment, highlighting the ongoing need for targeted training and development in specialized knowledge.

Methods to Address Skill Gaps

The next question explored the methods used to address skill gaps within the workforce. Respondents primarily favored practical approaches (Figure 14):

- "Hands-on approach, with learning by doing and making mistakes": 71%,
- "Shadowing under supervision of more experienced staff": 54%,
- "Further training provided": 46%,
- "No special measure": 19%,
- "Hire new staff": 10%.

Ranking of skills according to their importance

RM's employers were asked to rank the nine skill families (the skills of table 1) on a scale from 1 (not important) to 5 (extremely important). Table 2 shows the resulting ranking, with 'Transversal skills' (mean 4.5) in the first position, followed by 'Specialized knowledge for research performing organizational contexts' (mean 4.4). 'Outreach and Community' (mean 3.7) and 'Line management of others (Talent Development)' (mean 3.5) hold the second-to-last and last positions, respectively."

Table 2 – Ranking of skills according to importance (from 1 - not important - to 5 - extremely important) perceived by this questionnaire's respondents

Ranking by RMs' employers		MEAN
SKILLS		
1	Transversal skills	4,5
2	Specialised knowledge for research performing organisational contexts	4,4
3	Project Management	4,4
4	Communication	4,3
5	Relationship Management	4,3
6	Technical Skills	4,2
7	Financing/contracting/compliance	4,2
8	Outreach and Community	3,7
9	Line management of others (Talent Development)	3,5

It is interesting to compare these results with those obtained by posing the same question to different target groups. For example, in the initial CARDEA survey⁴³, where the survey's respondents were general RMs, not mainly RMs involved in colleague recruitment as in this survey.

In the initial CARDEA survey (Table 3), 'Transversal skills' were in the first position, perceived as the most important for performing the RM profession. This result aligns with the one obtained in this survey and was also seen in other surveys. For instance, in the 1st edition of the RAAAP survey⁴⁴, research administrators holding leadership positions assigned high importance to their soft skills, rating them as very or extremely important in more than 90% of the responses. Additionally, in the initial CARDEA survey, 'Outreach and Community' (mean 3.8) and 'Line management of others (Talent Development)' (mean 3.8) were at the bottom of the ranking, similar to the results of this new survey.

However, there is an interesting difference between this survey and the initial CARDEA survey: 'Specialized knowledge for research performing organizational contexts' was placed at the last position in the initial CARDEA survey ranking, whereas here it is in a top position. It appears that RM employers consider specialized knowledge important, while general RMs may view specialized knowledge as something that can be 'easily' acquired through work experience according to a learning-by-doing approach. In previous questions, RM employers noted a lack of specialized knowledge in candidates during selection processes and in not proficient colleagues. This could be a reason why they consider specialized knowledge to be among the important skills.

Table 3 - Ranking of skills according to importance (from 1 - not important - to 5 - extremely important) perceived by general RMs (data from initial CARDEA survey⁴⁵)

Ranking by RMs (data from initial CARDEA survey)		
SKILLS		MEAN
1	Transversal skills	4,3
2	Relationship management	4,2
3	Project Management	4,1
4	Financing/Contracting/Compliance	4,0
5	Technical skills	3,9
6	Communication	3,9
7	Line management of others (Talent Development)	3,8
8	Outreach and community	3,8
9	Specialised knowledge for research performing organisational contexts	3,7

Participation in Training Initiatives

The final part of the survey investigated whether institutions had participated in training initiatives over the past 24 months and the topics covered. A positive response was given by 81% of the respondents (Figure 15). The average duration of training is estimated around 13 hours per year.

The topics most frequently chosen for training included (Figure 16):

- Relationship management (58%),
- Specialised knowledge for research performing organisational contexts (57%).

Conversely, the topics with the lowest frequencies were:

- Outreach and community (15%),
- Line management of others (Talent Development) (13%).

⁴³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7882908>

⁴⁴ <https://inorms.net/activities/raaap-taskforce/raaap-outputs/>

⁴⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7882908>

Figure 12 – Estimation of RMs fully proficiency within an institution

Figure 13 – Typology of skills missing in RMs not fully proficiency

Figure 14 - Kind of adopted means used by an institution to remediate if a skill is missing on the workforce

Figure 15 – Percentage of institutions in which RMs participated in training course.

Figure 16 – Topics of training courses attended by RMs

Conclusions

The main findings of the analysis conducted through the survey targeting RMs' employers can be summarized as follows:

1. **High demand for RMs:** The labor market is actively seeking RMs. Employers reported difficulty in finding candidates and, more specifically, in finding appealing candidates. From the perspective of

training providers, this indicates a need to develop training programs that prepare new and specialised labor force for the job market as RMs.

2. **Focus on specialised knowledge in training:** Training programs should target newcomers to the RM profession and emphasize specialized knowledge. The training provided to new entrants should focus on “specialized knowledge in research management,” which is the competence most commonly lacking in RM candidates and the current workforce. Both “specialized knowledge in research management” and soft skills are perceived as highly important by RM employers. Furthermore, “specialized knowledge in research management” is frequently selected as a training topic, reinforcing the idea that there is a significant gap in these competencies.
3. **Limited relevance of professional certification:** During the recruitment process, the evaluation of certified professional qualifications is not highly relevant. This could be attributed to the rarity of such certifications among candidates.
4. **Preferred methods for upskilling:** Institutions prefer hands-on approaches to upskill their workforce. When a skill is missing, institutions typically rely on a hands-on approach, incorporating learning by doing and allowing for mistakes, or on shadowing under the supervision of more experienced staff.

These findings suggest that training providers should prioritise specialised knowledge and practical, experience-based learning methods to better prepare candidates for the RM profession. Additionally, there may be a need to increase the availability and recognition of professional certifications in research management to enhance their relevance in the hiring process.

3.3.3 The perspective of opinion leaders

Context

In order to better understand the role of RMs, based on the perspectives of the other actors of a research and innovation ecosystem, CARDEA expanded the scope of the investigation to include some key figures that were named “opinion leaders”.

Opinion leaders are experts of the ERA principles and in the meantime persons that know very well both the researcher profession (and, consequently, researchers’ needs), and the valuable contribution that RMs can give to research ecosystems.

Their perspective was important to CARDEA to deepen what the real expected skills for RMs are, with the ultimate goal of shaping training modules for RMs based also on researchers’ needs. Indeed, these opinion leaders have a comprehensive overview of the whole scenario composed by the ERA, the researchers and the RMs. They can link the dots of the multiple needs of these three stakeholders.

Having this goal in mind, CARDEA involved in their analysis the ERAC (European Research Area and Innovation Committee), since this is the EU’s strategic policy advisory committee on topics related to research and innovation. And among the six ERAC sub-groups, which are in charge of advancing and monitoring specific ERA priorities, CARDEA involved members of the Standing Working Group on Human Resources and Mobility (SWG HRM), specifically the experts that were participating in the review of the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (C&C).

Methodology

In June and July 2023, CARDEA sent invitations to members of the Standing Working Group on Human Resources and Mobility (SWG HRM) and to experts involved in the review of the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (C&C). Seven experts accepted CARDEA’s invitation, and TEAMS meetings were scheduled for the end of September and the beginning of October.

The names of the seven interviewed persons were:

- Raul Delgado Morales
- Karen Vandeveldel
- Isabel Strauss
- Conor O’Carroll
- Gareth O’Neill
- Clare Vinay
- Fulvio Esposito

Before the start of the interviews, participants signed an informed consent form. This form provided information about the CARDEA project and informed participants that the interviews would be recorded, with only the following anonymized excerpts being made public.

The goal of the interviews was to understand the experts’ perspectives on the future of the RM profession and how it should evolve to meet the needs of EU researchers and align with ERA priorities. The interviews lasted approximately 30 to 60 minutes, beginning with the following five standard questions for all interviewees, followed by an open discussion.

The recordings are stored confidentially. Below are the core results of the interviews, which have been anonymized to ensure that no specific identities are associated with any statements.

Results

Here below are reported the summaries of the 7 interviews.

1. **Who are RMs? What is your definition of research management? What is the main role of RMs in a research organization and in the research and innovation ecosystem?**

The opinion leaders agreed that defining the profession of a RM is challenging due to its **variety of roles and tasks**. In general, RMs were described as individuals who **enable the entire cycle of research**, ideally divided into three domains: pre-award stage, post-award implementation, and research results valorization. The research activity was described as a **co-creation** process, where RMs work in partnership with researchers.

One interviewee emphasised the importance of using the term "people enabling research" rather than "people supporting research," arguing that the latter phrase has a **misleading ancillary connotation**. The opinion leader stated that without the work of RMs, research would not occur, highlighting that the research enterprise is a team effort where each role is crucial. Using incorrect terminology can contribute to a lack of parity of esteem between RMs and researchers. Common terms used to describe RMs revolve around the concept of "**relationships**". RMs were defined as **connectors, mediators, facilitators, coordinators, intermediators, communicators, and problem solvers**. They bridge the world of research with external stakeholders at both local (e.g. local productive systems) and international levels. Figurative expressions like "**stakeholder managers**", "**gap fillers**" and "**knowledge brokers**" were used to illustrate that RMs trade in knowledge, facilitating its circulation, sharing, and development rather than creating it themselves. RMs are knowledgeable about funders' rules and regulations, the administrative aspects of research, and they analyze and solve complex problems—sometimes with creative solutions. Additionally, RMs were recognized as skilled in coaching and managing people.

Beyond the definition of generalist profile, it was recognised that RMs can specialize in various areas based on their professional responsibilities. They may support researchers in skills development and training, open science and research valorization, IP management, HR management, and data management, among others.

One opinion leader disagreed with the term "research managers", arguing that the word "manager" implies RMs are responsible for the research itself, its outcomes and research data, which is not the case in support offices. Instead, they proposed terms like "**research developers**", emphasizing their role in skill development. This perspective excludes PhD supervisors, professors, deans, and rectors from being classified as RMs, as these individuals are the "true managers" of research, responsible for its direction and outcomes. According to this view, it is premature to define RMs without first detailing their specific roles.

Ideally, RMs should have a PhD, not because of its legal value, but because it demonstrates familiarity with the research world, its opportunities, and challenges. However, requiring a PhD for RMs was seen as potentially narrowing the labor market too much.

2. **What are the key technical skills (i.e. project management, ethics) and transversal skills (i.e. communication) skills you believe a research manager should have in order to perform the job well and which one(s) you feel are more important?**

Opinion leaders agree that RMs need to be **multi-skilled**, possessing a diverse set of abilities and a mindset that allows them to work across various fields.

Given the role of RMs as mediators, transversal skills are deemed crucial for the profession. Key transversal skills include teamwork and management, leadership, critical thinking, negotiation ability, flexibility, quick learning and decision-making, time management, adaptability to

different situations and stakeholders, planning, foresight, initiating change, tolerating frustration and others' decisions, and accepting not always being heard by senior researchers. Specifically, **empathy and communication skills** were highlighted as top transversal skills. These are essential within a research institution and crucial for engaging stakeholders, networking with private entities, and fostering an entrepreneurial attitude.

Overall, the importance of **T-shaped competencies** was emphasized: a foundation of strong transversal skills complemented by deep knowledge in one or more specific technical subjects relevant to their role. Examples of such technical subjects include lab technologies, ethics, intellectual property, technology transfer, statistics for decision-making, knowledge of rules and regulations, financial competencies, and auditing. Understanding the entire research process and system, from beginning to end, was also identified as an important technical competence.

One opinion leader highlighted that research management is inherently a team effort, and it is unrealistic for one person or a small group to possess all the necessary skills and competencies. Therefore, it is often preferred to have a specialized, centralized research support office that serves multiple research institutions within a region, rather than many small offices dedicated to individual organizations.

As a result of this multi-skilled nature, opinion leaders emphasized the need for a comprehensive training path for RMs, covering all aspects of the profession, even though this could be time-consuming. They advocated for **international and inter-sectoral mobility** to be integral to the training path for RMs in the EU.

3. **Do you think that instruments similar to ResearchComp, European Charter for Researchers or EURAXESS that are applied for researchers could be extended to the professional figure of RMs? Or they are only a starting point, a sort of a model from which to build specific and dedicated instruments for RMs?**

Note that in the new European Charter for Researchers it is reported that: “The profiles R1-R4 are strictly of relevance for researchers and are not relevant for research management. Similar types of profiles might be considered for research management once the category is adequately framed”.

According to most opinion leaders, there is significant **overlap between the roles of researchers and RMs**, and the distinction between the two is often unclear. Indeed, some researchers may take on roles typically associated with RMs, as research management is part of their responsibilities. Additionally, some training programs could be suitable for both researchers and RMs.

However, most opinion leaders agree on the **importance of keeping the two professions separate**. Despite the overlap in certain professional aspects, the ResearchComp framework is not entirely applicable to RMs. It could, however, serve as a starting point for building a framework specific to RMs. As one opinion leader stated, “some skills of the ResearchComp could be suitable for RMs, but I don’t think it’s good to link the profession of RM to that of the researcher. RMs are not researchers who failed, and it is not necessary to have a PhD to be a good RM.” Another opinion leader added, “ResearchComp is just for researchers as it defines the track for researchers, not for other profiles. Each support staff category has its own track.”

Similarly, another opinion leader emphasised that the RM profession must stand on its own and suggested creating a **dedicated framework for RMs**: “Building a framework for RMs is more challenging compared to researchers, as the researcher career has some ‘fixed’ milestones, such as obtaining a PhD, which help delineate the different levels. For RMs, it is not as straightforward.

The framework should list core competencies and describe what RMs actually do. It could be organized into four levels, RM1-RM4, with the senior level being the director of a research center. This framework should provide a career path, explain how people progress, how to map progress, and tie it to institutional structures. We should avoid using ResearchComp, as it is too detailed and focused on researchers' careers, whereas RMs should have their own framework linked to administrative and managerial spheres."

Opinion leaders believe that it is beneficial for some researchers to become RMs at some point in their careers. RM could be a career option for researchers, allowing for the transfer of professionals between the two fields. There should be no discrimination; recognizing the diversity of the two professions and facilitating transfers between them can enhance the effectiveness of both roles. RMs should understand more about research, while researchers should learn more about research management, ensuring both groups speak the same language. It is beneficial to have a clear distinction between research activities and RM roles to avoid confusion. Having a PhD is considered advantageous but not necessary for being an RM.

A framework structured according to levels R1-R4 was recognized as helpful to clarify the RM profession. However, it is expected to take time before such a framework is widely adopted, as RM careers are less standardised across the EU compared to researchers' careers.

Tools like **EURAXESS could be extended to RMs**, helping to advertise job openings, support mobility, and develop career paths. Similarly, learning platforms could facilitate networking among RMs, especially across different areas of expertise and countries within the EU, aiding in the standardization of the profession and types of contracts.

In summary, opinion leaders advocate for the **distinct recognition and professionalisation of RMs**, emphasizing the need for a dedicated framework, increased visibility, and a clear career path. They also stress the importance of fostering collaboration and mutual understanding between researchers and RMs to enhance the overall effectiveness of research management.

4. **Which are the obstacles towards the acknowledgement of the professional figure of research manager?**

According to opinion leaders, raising awareness about the value of research management within the R&I ecosystem is crucial, particularly to improve the perception RMs have of themselves and the perception that senior leadership in academia (governance level) has about research management.

In some instances, opinion leaders have observed that RMs can be their own biggest obstacle due to a **lack of self-confidence**. There have been cases where shifts from a researcher's career to research management were viewed as failures because of a lack of awareness about the value of RMs. Compared to researchers, RMs are often seen as inferior and not a valuable career option. Opinion leaders emphasized the **urgency of creating a culture of research management**, professionalizing RMs, providing clear career progression, and making them feel part of the institution's success. They stressed the importance of building evidence to ensure that RMs are taken seriously and no longer remain invisible. As they put it, "It is necessary to invest in and value the profession so that every part is understood and acknowledged. It's important to account for the value RM adds, such as the percentage of grant wins and the amount of money coming from grants. Providing evidence helps achieve parity of esteem and understand what works better and what doesn't."

On the other side, it is crucial to involve senior leadership in the **awareness campaign** to make them conscious of the value RMs bring to institutions. This change will lead to more staff entering

the role, increased professionalisation, and the avoidance of short-term contracts. A proper impact and evaluation framework is necessary to assess the value of RM.

One opinion leader openly criticized the prevalent hierarchical mindset in academia, which does **not see professional parity between researchers and RMs** in terms of knowledge creation, salary, perception, contract length, and challenges. All opinion leaders agreed that research is a team effort and not just the result of a single principal investigator (PI). There is an urgent need to change the perception academics have towards RMs and to define how to reward RMs, not just the PI. While PIs focus on research topics and are at the top of the iceberg, RMs are often at the bottom, not always visible but crucial.

The lack of a clear identity, defined training, and career paths means RMs remain **invisible**. RMs need to be clearly defined so they cannot be moved from their roles and are "not-exchangeable" with other administrative roles within an institution.

Regarding training paths, opinion leaders noted that the skills needed by RMs, especially transversal ones (e.g., critical thinking, problem-solving), are difficult to prove, recognize, and certify (for example, through a master's degree), which is another obstacle to acknowledging the professional figure of RM.

One opinion leader expressed frustration that RMs are spending too much time agreeing on a definition, which is not helping progress any further.

5. **Which solutions or policies do you envisage to valorize the professional figure of research manager into the ERA?**

Opinion leaders view a **career framework** as crucial for recognising and specifically defining the profession of RM. They believe that a clear career progression is essential for attracting talented individuals to the role of RMs. While some opinion leaders preferred a more generalist career framework, others advocated for a tailored framework for each profile within research management. One opinion leader suggested promoting the RM career framework within institutions by depicting it as a useful, relevant, and attractive tool, a key to the institution's success. They proposed linking it to the "**Excellence in Research**" award, suggesting that implementing the RM career framework could be included in the action plans of institutions seeking this award.

Opinion leaders agreed on the importance of increasing the visibility of RMs in order to enhance their professional status within the ERA. To achieve this, they proposed the following actions:

- **Depict RMs as Key to Securing Funds:** Demonstrate that increasing the number of RMs leads to a higher success rate in obtaining research funds by collecting and sharing success stories.
- **Mention the Profession in Funding Schemes and Policy Documents:** Ensure that the role of RMs is explicitly mentioned in relevant documents.
- **Continue Lobbying through EU Associations of RMs:** Advocate for the profession at the European level.
- **Promote RM as a Career Destination:** Once the profession has a clear structure and career progression with dedicated training, it is important to highlight the career path not only for those transitioning from research but also for individuals from other professions and students.

To avoid fixed-term contracts for RMs, one opinion leader suggested adopting measures similar to those proposed for researchers in the "COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on a European

framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe"⁴⁶. This includes resolute actions to **counter precarity and support job security and stability**. Specifically, they proposed setting a maximum total duration for fixed-term appointments and ensuring that fixed-term contracts do not exceed one-third of the overall RM human resources of a given employer. Opinion leaders are aware that losing trained RMs represents a waste of time and money for institutions. Therefore, they advocate for institutional investment in RMs as a strategy to secure funding and improve the overall quality of research.

In summary, **establishing a robust career framework, enhancing visibility, and ensuring job security** for RMs are key strategies identified by opinion leaders to professionalize and strengthen the role of RMs in the ERA.

Conclusions

The following conclusions can be summarized from the interviews with opinion leaders:

RM Identity/Role/Skills

- **The challenge of a RM definition:** defining a "research manager" is challenging due to the wide variety of roles and tasks they perform.
- **Enablers of research:** RMs were defined as people who enable the entire research cycle (pre-award, post-award, tech-transfer), not merely support it, as "support" has an ancillary connotation.
- **RM "relationships role":** the definitions of RM proposed by opinion leaders include terms from the semantics of "relation," such as "connectors," "mediators," "facilitators," "coordinators," "intermediaries," "communicators," "problem solvers," "stakeholder managers," "gap fillers," and "knowledge brokers."
- **Transversal skills:** given their role as mediators, transversal skills are vital for RMs. Top transversal skills include empathy and communication.
- **T-shaped competence:** effective RMs should possess T-shaped competence, combining strong transversal skills with deep knowledge in specific technical subjects relevant to their role.
- **Complex training path:** due to the multi-skilled nature of the profession, a comprehensive, 360-degree training path is essential for RMs, even if it is time-consuming. International and inter-sectoral **mobility** should be integral to this training path.
- **Educational background:** ideally, RMs should have a PhD, not for its legal value but to demonstrate familiarity with the research world and its challenges. However, making a PhD a requirement could overly restrict the labor market.

Acknowledging the Professional Figure of RM

- **Separated careers for RMs and researchers:** The RM profession should not be linked to that of researchers, since it stands by itself. RMs need their own framework and career path. A framework structured according to levels RM1-RM4 was recognized as helpful for clarifying the RM profession.
- **Extended Tools and Platforms:** Tools like EURAXESS and learning platforms typically used by researchers could be extended to RMs to advertise job openings, support mobility, develop career paths, and facilitate networking. This would aid also in the standardization of RM profession and contract types across the EU.
- **Raising Awareness:** There is a need to increase awareness of the value of RMs among themselves and at the governance level of institutions. Creating a culture of research management is urgent, particularly to improve the perception of senior leadership in academia about research management. One opinion leader criticized the prevalent hierarchical mindset in academia that

⁴⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/C/2023/1640/oj>

does not see professional parity between researchers and RMs in terms of knowledge creation, salary, perception, contract length, and challenges.

- **Building Evidence:** It is crucial to build evidence to prove the value of RMs, such as the percentage and amount of grants obtained with and without their involvement.
- **Rewarding mechanism for RMs:** All opinion leaders agreed that research is a team effort and not just the result of a single principal investigator (PI). There is an urgent need to change the academic perception towards RMs and to define how to reward RMs, not just the PI.
- **Career Framework:** Opinion leaders view a career framework as crucial for recognizing and specifically defining the RM profession. To incentivize the use of such a framework, they proposed linking it to the "Excellence in Research" award, suggesting that implementing the RM career framework could be included in the action plans of institutions seeking this award.
- **Countering Precarity:** It is essential for opinion leaders to take resolute actions to address job precarity and support job security and stability for RMs.
- **Promoting RM as a Career Destination:** Once the profession has a clear structure and career progression with dedicated training, it is important to highlight the career path not only for those transitioning from research but also for individuals from other professions and students.

4 - CARDEA training modules: how they are implemented

As mentioned in the introduction, the overall objective of CARDEA work package 7 “Training and development” is to develop a comprehensive training programme designed by and for RMs, based on the deep analysis of RMs needs.

Needs of RMs have been duly investigated by analysing the results of recent surveys, including the one conducted by CARDEA, targeting only RMs (see “Dataset for Cardea Research Manager Survey 2022”⁴⁷). In addition, in order to further guarantee the quality and effectiveness of the CARDEA training, CARDEA strategically considered also needs and expectations of other key figures working with RMs (i.e. researchers, research institutions, universities and other stakeholders).

Based on the two analytical approaches described above, this section provides the main features of the CARDEA training modules, that was agreed by CARDEA partners. This analysis and the justifications supporting these choices could be useful to others that are planning a training path specifically tailored to RMs.

4.1 Target

The exclusive target group of CARDEA training modules are RMs.

Currently, there are many training courses that are delivered for researchers and open to RMs or vice versa. CARDEA does believe that RMs need a **specific training enabling them to better support research and researchers**, and that the recognition of RM profession is marked also by this “cultural” change. No one would even think to organize a training event for nurses which also targets doctors and vice versa. For sure, there would be some common topics, but the level of detail and the learning objectives are different!

Designing contents specifically for RMs means, for example, that topics such as those ones related to the EU research policies (Open science, gender-oriented research, etc) are addressed in a way that that a specific topic is introduced and deepened, but the ultimate learning outcome is also to **learn how to provide a high quality support to researchers or research institutions with regard to it** (through e.g. the presentation of best practices and concrete cases of support, mechanisms of rewarding, training and raising awareness initiatives).

Within the target group of RMs, CARDEA training modules will **mainly target RM1 - First Stage Research Manager (newcomers in the profession)** according to the CARDEA Profile Framework for Research Manager Careers⁴⁸ (RM1-RM2). Nevertheless, CARDEA training modules can be **concomitantly useful for more senior staff** who are willing to deepen their understanding of a particular aspect of the research management profession that they are not very familiar with.

The CARDEA training modules consist of several training modules that are all together a comprehensive training to people new in the profession – a sort of **core learning** common to all categories of RMs.

A comprehensive training for newcomers is an added value for the current RM community as:

- currently the labor market is actively seeking RMs but has difficulty in finding figures with adequate skills, as we have seen from our investigation. Employers reported difficulty in finding candidates and, more specifically, in finding appealing candidates, already experienced in research management. This indicates a need to develop training programs that prepare new and specialized

⁴⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/7882908>

⁴⁸ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/competenceframework/>

labor force for the job market as RMs. The training provided by CARDEA is focused on “specialized knowledge in research management,” which, according to our investigation, is the competence most commonly lacking in RM candidates for new positions and the current workforce;

- it is a publicly available one-stop shop for employers that otherwise have to rely on different training providers and spend time and effort to train newcomers. In the HETFA survey, 80.2% of respondents agree or strongly agree on the fact that the training of newcomers is a long process which needs a lot of investment especially considering wide variety of special skills and knowledge needed for the job and the competitive, uncertain and volatile nature of the work environment;
- it could be a tool that newcomers can use to understand their role and which skills are needed when applying for the job. It can set the expectations about the job;
- it is a free training so a precious resource especially for RMs that are at the beginning of their career or still unemployed and could not have specific funds available dedicated for training;
- once it is completed, it is a proof of evidence to demonstrate the knowledge and an initial expertise into the topics of research management and it is useful during selection processes both to employer and aspiring employee.

4.2 Format

The CARDEA training programme will consist of 17 **modules** to be delivered through **free on-line recorded lessons**.

The choice of this format is aligned to the need of **flexibility**, due to the fact that context in which RMs operate is complex and variable and training modules should adapt to this context. Indeed, according to the analysed surveys (HETFA and EARMA PDRC), the respondents envisaged a formal training in which the critical question is not length, but rather flexibility and practicality.

Since the CARDEA training programme is composed by several training modules, the fruition of the training can be arranged based on the specific needs of the participants in terms of time and background knowledge of the participants (e.g. a RM can select specific topics according to their own needs).

The choice of this specific format was also done to make the training more **inclusive**. Participation through on-line webinars allows all potential participants to enjoy the training, without sustaining costs related to travel and accommodation. In this sense, CARDEA will offer a “democratic training”, since it will offer a high-quality training for all, especially for RMs that are at the beginning of their career and could not have specific funds available dedicated for training (this is often the case of RMs from Widening countries or from small organisations, e.g. associations, NGOs). In addition, the improvement of the quality of the training means in the long run to enhance the quality of research support, and this is a way to spread the excellence across Europe according to the principle that “none must be left behind”.

4.3 Content

The CARDEA training modules were shaped to cover the main competences areas of the CARDEA framework for RMs. The CARDEA Research Manager Competency Framework⁴⁹ is organized in 3 main levels:

- 8 main competence areas:
 - Cognitive Abilities/Transversal Skills
 - Technical Proficiency
 - Subject Matter Expertise/Specialised Knowledge
 - Research Project Oversight
 - Community Engagement
 - Line Management and Talent Development

⁴⁹ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/competenceframework/>

- Communication
- Relationship Management
- 42 competencies
- 672 learning outcomes along 4 proficiency levels (foundational, intermediate, advanced, expert).

Within the framework, each competency includes learning outcomes for each proficiency level. It is not expected that RMs acquire the highest level of proficiency or have the same proficiency across all the 8 competence areas. However, it is envisaged that Researcher Managers develop their skills in all 8 competence areas where possible.

For such reasons, the CARDEA consortium has fixed as learning objective of its modules to provide training for RMs covering all competence areas of the profession. The CARDEA modules are a **core learning common**

to all categories of RMs (i.e. Data Manager, Research Project Manager, Research Integrity Manager and Outreach Manager), a comprehensive training covering the main aspect of research management profession. Among the 8 main competences areas, the CARDEA training has a special focus on subject matter expertise in research management, so specialized knowledge for research performing organizational contexts.

Being the target of CARDEA mainly the category of RM1, the learning module will focus on **foundational level competences of the RM Comp**. Specifically, the learning outcomes of each training module refer to the foundational level of each competence.

For example, the learning outcomes of the module concerning “data stewardship” refer to the foundational level of this competence, which corresponds to the left column of the below table:

3. Data Stewardship			
FOUNDATIONAL	INTERMEDIATE	ADVANCED	EXPERT
Responsible and ethical handling of research data as an organisational asset and its role in decision-making	Conducts data profiling to assess data quality and identifies areas for improvement	Implements data management strategies for critical data elements	Provides leadership in establishing and leading organisational data governance initiatives
Recognises basic principles of data quality and the impact of poor data quality on outcomes	Able to apply metadata management practices to enhance data discoverability and traceability	Demonstrates advanced understanding of data privacy and security principles and implements measures to protect sensitive data	Introduces innovative approaches to data management, including the integration of emerging technologies
Grasps foundational concepts of data governance, including roles and responsibilities	Ability to classify data based on sensitivity and usage requirements to ensure proper handling	Collaborates with stakeholders across the organisation to align data stewardship practices with research objectives	Possesses expertise in navigating and ensuring compliance with evolving data regulations and standards
Understands basic data compliance requirements and their implications for stewardship	Participates in the implementation of data governance frameworks and policies (i.e. GDPR, FOI)	Develops and implements data lifecycle management strategies, including archiving and purging	Contributes to the development of an overarching data strategy aligned with organisational, national and international research goals

The CARDEA training module are in total 17, of which:

- 7 modules are covering the main competences areas of the RM Comp Framework, except for the area called “subject matter expertise”; specifically:

- Cognitive Abilities/Transversal Skills;
- Research Project Oversight;
- Community Engagement;
- Line Management and Talent Development;
- Communication;
- Relationship Management;
- Technical Proficiency. This module is focusing on the novelty of the use of Artificial Intelligence tools in the context of research management.

- 9 modules are specific for the competence area of the “subject matter expertise”, which is the area with the specialised knowledge for research management profession; specifically:

- Pre-Award;
- Post Award;
- Managing equality, diversity and inclusion (including gender, disability and racism);
- Data Stewardship;
- Technology Transfer;
- HR Research – Employment, training etc.;
- Research Finance;

- Clinical Research Management;
- Research Ethics and Integrity.

- 1 module is an innovative training on “How to embed the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) in the overall research management”. Since all CARDEA partners have huge expertise on the HRS4R initiative, this module presents how to make sure that the enhancement of the research management support is part of the overall effort of a research organization to improve its research environment. More specifically, the module explains the process of HRS4R initiative and offers a case study with examples of how to create synergies among the different departments dealing with research management and maximize its impact.

4.4 Trainers

The CARDEA training modules are mainly developed by the CARDEA partners. The module on the use of Artificial Intelligence in research management context is presented by an expert, hired on purpose by CARDEA for such specific and new topic. Otherwise, in general, each of the CARDEA partner developed 2 modules.

4.5 Micro-credentials

CARDEA training modules are certified through micro-credentials which are, according to the EU definition, the records of the learning outcomes that a learner has acquired following a small volume of learning (see EU approach to micro-credentials, December 2021). The micro-credential is recorded in an open badge that will be issued by the University of Macerata, leader of CARDEA WP 7 “Training and development”.

The competences certified by the CARDEA open badge corresponds to the foundational level of the CARDEA RM Competences Framework.

The choice of open badge is justified by its flexibility and practicality, especially for the participants to the training. Indeed, the micro-credentials recorded in the open badge is a proof of the acquired competences during the learning path. A document that can be presented at international level during hiring processes, career progression procedures, or when starting a new job position.

4.6 CARDEA training modules syllabus

The following paragraph is the syllabus of the CARDEA training modules.

For all the modules the main target audience is RM1 - First Stage Research Manager (newcomers in the profession) of the CARDEA Profile Framework for Research Manager Careers⁵⁰ (RM1-RM4). Nevertheless, the training could also concomitantly useful to more expert staff that could choose some topics according to their own needs.

The level of the module is foundational, according to the proficiency level of the CARDEA Competences Framework for RMs⁵¹.

⁵⁰ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/competenceframework/>

⁵¹ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/competenceframework/>

Number and title and of the module: **Module 1 - Pre-Award**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: The module gives practical advice to RMs for all the important steps on the preparation of a proposal in Horizon Europe framework programme. More specifically focuses on the identification of the appropriate funding opportunities, the selection of the proposal partners and the formation of the consortium and useful hints and tips for the preparation of the proposal and the budget.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 – Identification of Appropriate Funding Opportunities**
- Author: Pierantonios Papazoglou
- Institution: European University Cyprus
- Description of the video: The video presents the mechanisms and approaches for the identification of appropriate funding opportunities on Horizon Europe framework programme. More specifically presents the Horizon Europe at a glance and the proper ways to search the appropriate funding in it. It analyzes the opportunities for individual career development but also for organizations forming consortia.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 – Partner Search and Consortium Formation**
- Author: Pierantonios Papazoglou
- Institution: European University Cyprus
- Description of the video: The video presents effective strategies for partner search and consortium formation for securing funding from the Horizon Europe framework programme. More specifically, it outlines the qualities that make a partner a strong candidate and the characteristics that a consortium should have to be balanced and potentially successful. Finally, the video also presents methods for finding relevant partners.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 – Overall Proposal – Preparation Hints & Tips**
- Author: Pierantonios Papazoglou
- Institution: European University Cyprus
- Description of the video: The video provides valuable tips and guidance for preparing a Horizon Europe proposal. It outlines the proposal's context within Horizon Europe and offers targeted advice to support each step of the writing process.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 4 – Budget Preparation**
- Author: Maria-Thalia Christou
- Institution: European University Cyprus
- Description of the video: The video offers practical tips for proposal preparation, focusing specifically on key financial principles. It explains how to present the budget in Parts A and B of the proposal and provides useful advice for preparing an effective budget for Horizon Europe or other research projects. Additionally, it highlights available guidance resources and essential documents.

NUMBER AND TITLE AND OF THE MODULE: **Module 2 - Post-Award**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: The module offers an overview of the main obligations included in the Grant Agreement of Horizon Europe funded proposals, which are applicable also to other EU programmes. Specifically, the module presents the contents of the Grant Agreement and how to respect the ethics principles and open science requirements during project implementation. Key aspects of the Consortium Agreement are also presented.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 - Legal Aspects**
- Author: Barbara Chiuconi
- Institution: University of Macerata
- Description of the video: The video is an introduction to the legal framework regulating the implementation of an EU-funded project, examining the two key documents that form the legal basis of an EU-funded project: the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 - Ethics Requirements**
- Author: Erica Feliziani
- Institution: University of Macerata
- Description of the video: The video presents the key principles of ethics, security, and research integrity, along with the relevant legal framework. Additionally, it provides examples of how to address common ethical and security issues and explains the ethics appraisal process within a research project.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 - Open Science Requirements**
- Author: Erica Feliziani
- Institution: University of Macerata
- Description of the video: The video outlines the key recommended and mandatory practices for Open Science as outlined in Horizon Europe Grant Agreements. These include open access to publications, research data management, measures to ensure reproducibility of results, Citizen Science, early and open sharing of research, and open peer review.

NUMBER AND TITLE AND OF THE MODULE: **Module 3 - Managing Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (including Gender, Disability and Racism)**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module provides an in-depth understanding of the concepts of equity, equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) in the context of workplaces and research teams. It highlights the role of EDI in fostering innovative, productive, and fair environments. Topics include an exploration of unconscious biases and stereotypes, their various types, and effective strategies for mitigating them. The module also identifies common barriers to EDI, outlines strategic approaches to overcoming these challenges, and provides real-world examples of successful EDI practices.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 - What do we mean by EDI?**
- Author: Żaneta Świątkowska-Warkocka
- Institution: Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Description of the video: this introductory video defines key terms—Equality, Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion—and explains their importance in the workplace and research teams. It explores the impact of EDI on innovation, decision-making, and employee satisfaction.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 - Unconscious biases and stereotypes**
- Author: Żaneta Świątkowska-Warkocka
- Institution: Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Description of the video: This video explores unconscious bias and stereotypes in the workplace and research teams. Defines unconscious bias and stereotypes, and shows how they can affect decision-making and interactions. Presents strategies for recognizing and mitigating unconscious bias and stereotypes.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 - Equality legislation; Social inclusion**
- Author: Żaneta Świątkowska-Warkocka
- Institution: Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Description of the video: This video addresses the significance of language, behavior, and actions in creating an inclusive workplace. It introduces equality laws that ensure fair treatment and non-discrimination and discusses social inclusion's role in building a supportive, diverse environment.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 4 - Strategy**
- Author: Żaneta Świątkowska-Warkocka
- Institution: Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Description of the video: This video discusses the barriers that hinder effective EDI integration in the workplace. It offers strategies for embedding equality, diversity, and inclusion and includes real-world examples of successful EDI initiatives.

NUMBER AND TITLE AND OF THE MODULE: **Module 4 - Data Stewardship**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: In this module, students can explore key data management concepts essential for a data steward, including FAIR data principles, open data practices, and various data typologies. The module covers the entire life cycle of research data: from planning, collection, and processing to analysis, storage, and protection. These fundamentals form the basis of the Data Management Plan (DMP), a core deliverable for data stewards. Legal aspects and data quality considerations are also discussed.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 - Introduction**
- Author: Lluís Rovira
- Institution: AGAUR, Agency for Management of University and Research Grants
- Description of the video: This introductory video defines the emerging role of the data steward and provides guidance for RMs on the foundational steps of data management.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 - Data management plan**
- Author: Lluís Rovira
- Institution: AGAUR, Agency for Management of University and Research Grants
- Description of the video: This video explores the Data Management Plan (DMP) in depth, covering each stage of the research data life cycle: planning, collection, processing, analysis, storage, and protection.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 - Legal issues**
- Author: Lluís Rovira
- Institution: AGAUR, Agency for Management of University and Research Grants
- Description of the video: This video addresses the legal aspects of data management, focusing on the handling of sensitive data categories to ensure compliance with regulations. Practical examples, including a curious one, are included to illustrate potential legal pitfalls.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 4 - Research data quality**
- Author: Lluís Rovira
- Institution: AGAUR, Agency for Management of University and Research Grants
- Description of the video: This video examines the concept of data quality in research. It discusses methods for assessing, improving, and managing data quality and highlights future challenges and long-term benefits of maintaining high-quality research data.

NUMBER AND TITLE AND OF THE MODULE: **Module 5 – Technology Transfer**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module offers a general overview of technology transfer and it presents a selection of topics related to the Third Mission of the university, knowledge co-creation and innovation intermediaries. Students will learn the key features of the TM, the main challenges to the implementation of technology transfer, and the transformation towards the civic university. Furthermore, students will get insights into the role of innovation intermediaries in the ecosystems where universities operate.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 - The Third Mission of the University**
- Author: Lorenzo Compagnucci
- Institution: University of Macerata
- Description of the video: The video presents a selection of insights into the Third Mission of the university. The video focuses on the concept, features and evolution of the TM. Furthermore, it outlines the main challenges to TM implementation, especially in the field of the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 - Innovation ecosystems and intermediaries**
- Author: Dominique Lepore
- Institution: University of Macerata
- Description of the video: The video explores the complexities of innovation ecosystems, the principles of open innovation, and the roles of innovation intermediaries. It offers deep insights into how these components stimulate innovation and drive transformative change across industries.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 - A paradigm for knowledge valorization and co-creation**
- Author: Francesca Spigarelli
- Institution: University of Macerata
- Description of the video: The video presents the different approaches to Third Mission of university using the helix models and dives into the broader concept of civic university. It analyses the changes required to universities in the contemporary context, where they not only have to prepare future generations, but also need to nurture and guide local communities in their path to sustainable and inclusive development. The transformation from Technology Transfer Office to Offices for social engagement is discussed.

NUMBER AND TITLE AND OF THE MODULE: **Module 6 – HR Research**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module equips HR research managers with the knowledge and skills to manage human resources effectively. The module focuses on key areas such as HR fundamentals, researcher recruitment, onboarding, and personnel management, ensuring compliance with institutional policies and legal frameworks.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title of the video: **Video 1 - Understanding HR Fundamentals for HR Research Managers**
- Author: Dr Olivia O'Leary
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video introduces the fundamental HR concepts needed for managing employment relationships within research organisations, covering recruitment, onboarding, performance management, and compliance with employment laws and policies.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 2 - Researcher Recruitment**
- Author: Dr Olivia O'Leary
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video covers the strategic process of researcher recruitment, including an open, transparent, merit-based recruitment process. It also discusses the importance of defining roles, creating inclusive job descriptions, and conducting interviews to build a diverse and skilled research team.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 3 - Onboarding and Orientation**
- Author: Dr Olivia O'Leary
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video explains how to effectively onboard and orient new research staff, ensuring they adapt quickly and integrate smoothly into the organisational culture through structured onboarding processes

- Number and title of the video: **Video 4 - Personnel Management and Compliance**
- Author: Dr Olivia O'Leary
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video highlights best practices in personnel management, including maintaining accurate records, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and handling non-EU researcher admission and residence.

NUMBER AND TITLE AND OF THE MODULE: **Module 7 - Research Finance**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module introduces the structure and key functions of a research finance office, covering essential concepts such as budgeting, income statements, balance sheets, cash flow, reporting, auditing, assets, liabilities, and equity. It also examines the financial dynamics within a research group and explores common funding sources available to support research initiatives.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 - Introduction and foundational concepts**
- Author: Lluís Rovira
- Institution: AGAUR, Agency for Management of University and Research Grants
- Description of the video: This video introduces foundational finance concepts for research management, covering essential topics like accounting, reporting, auditing, budget management, income statements, balance sheets, and cash flow statements to help avoid common pitfalls in financial oversight.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 - Organizing the unit of finances**
- Author: Lluís Rovira
- Institution: AGAUR, Agency for Management of University and Research Grants
- Description of the video: This video discusses the organization of a research finance office, presenting two models commonly used in research institutions and highlighting the critical role of the finance support office.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 - Research funding sources**
- Author: Lluís Rovira
- Institution: AGAUR, Agency for Management of University and Research Grants
- Description of the video: This video explores various research funding sources and strategies for success in a resource-constrained environment, including local, national, and EU funding opportunities, private funding, innovation revenues, and overhead management.

NUMBER AND TITLE AND OF THE MODULE: **Module 8 - Clinical Research Management**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module provides an introductory overview of clinical research management, focusing on fundamental concepts, ethical considerations, documentation, collaboration, and communication within clinical research. Learners will gain insights into managing clinical trials, ethical standards, and best practices for research documentation and communication.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title of the video: **Video 1 - Basic Understanding of Clinical Research Management**
- Author: Dr. Robert O'Connor
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video introduces learners to the key concepts and roles involved in clinical research management, including trial design, regulatory considerations, and the operational aspects of managing clinical studies.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 2 - Ethical Considerations in Clinical Research**
- Author: Dr. Robert O'Connor
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video explores the ethical frameworks and guidelines that govern clinical research. It highlights the importance of participant consent, privacy, and ensuring integrity in research practices.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 3 - Accurate and Organised Study Documentation**
- Author: Dr. Robert O'Connor
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video emphasizes the importance of maintaining accurate and organized documentation in clinical studies. It covers key aspects such as data integrity, audit readiness, and compliance with regulatory requirements.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 4 - Collaboration and Communication in Clinical Research**
- Author: Dr. Robert O'Connor
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video focuses on the critical role of collaboration and effective communication among clinical research teams, sponsors, and regulatory authorities to ensure successful study outcomes.

NUMBER AND TITLE AND OF THE MODULE: **Module 9 - Research Ethics and Integrity**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: The training module on Research Ethics and Integrity highlights the standards in the scientific research context emphasizing the four key layers of responsibility that ensure ethical practices. It highlights the specific roles of RMs in mentoring researchers and reporting misconduct. The module also explores the responsibilities related to planning research activities, with a focus on best practices for sharing results, including publishing, authorship, and citation rules, using IEEE guidelines as an example. Additionally, it addresses essential copyright principles, such as fair use and licensing, providing RMs with the tools to ensure compliance and protect intellectual property within their institutions.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 – Responsibilities in conducting scientific research**
- Author: Mihaela Albu
- Institution: Polytechnic University of Bucharest
- Description: The video is an introduction on research integrity specifying general standards for conducting research with details on each of the 4 (four) layers of responsibility. The specific responsibilities of RMs regarding mentorship and misbehavior reporting are also presented.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video Number 2 - Sharing research results**
- Author: Mihaela Albu
- Institution: Polytechnic University of Bucharest
- Description of the video: In this video, the responsibilities of research and RMs in planning activities are highlighted. In addition, the responsibilities regarding sharing results are presented with a focus on publishing and good practices in the professional communities using the example of authorship and citation rules the IEEE.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video 3 – Copyright**
- Author: Radu Plamanescu
- Institution: Polytechnic University of Bucharest
- Description of the video: This video focuses on essential copyright principles relevant to research and RMs' environments. It covers fair use, licensing, and best practices to ensure compliance and protect intellectual property within their institutions.

Number and title and of the module: **Module 10 – Cognitive Abilities/Transversal Skills**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module provides insights into the cognitive abilities essential for effective research management, focusing on cultural sensitivity, strategic planning, and creativity. Learners will understand the importance of these skills in fostering collaboration, adapting to diverse research environments, and enhancing decision-making processes.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE :

- Number and title of the video: **Video 1 - Cognitive Abilities: Introduction and Focus on Cultural Sensitivity and Strategic Planning**
- Authors: Véronique Larosa and Laurence Maquest
- Institution: University of Liège
- Description of the video: This video explores the role of cultural sensitivity and strategic planning in research management, emphasizing the value of recognizing diverse perspectives and effectively aligning research goals with strategic objectives.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 2 - Cognitive Abilities: Focus on Creativity**
- Author: Ingrid Chalant
- Institution: University of Liège – IINCO
- Description of the video: This video delves into the importance of creativity within research management, highlighting methods to foster innovative solutions and cross-disciplinary collaboration, which are vital for addressing complex research challenges and advancing organizational goals.

Number and title and of the module: **Module 11 – Research Project Oversight/Management**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module offers practical guidance on research project oversight and management. It is specifically designed for early-career or stage 1 RMs (RM1), equipping them with essential knowledge and actionable advice on effective oversight practices.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 1 - Managing the Research Project**
- Author: Ivona Peternel
- Institution: Juraj Dobrila University of Pula
- Video description: This training covers foundational aspects of research project management, including the project management cycle, the role of the RM, the structure of the research community, and distinctions between research funding and performing organizations.

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 2 - Establishing the Research Project Plan**
- Author: Ivona Peternel
- Institution: Juraj Dobrila University of Pula
- Video description: Focused on the initial planning phase, this video provides practical advice on developing a comprehensive project plan, managing risks, assigning tasks effectively, and implementing regular reporting practices.

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 3 - Managing project deliverables, monitoring and evaluation**
- Author: Ivona Peternel
- Institution: Juraj Dobrila University of Pula
- Video description: This training emphasizes the significance of defining project deliverables and introduces key concepts in monitoring and evaluation. Early-stage RMs (RM1) will learn to track and assess deliverables systematically, ensuring alignment with project goals and metrics.

Number and title and of the module: **Module 12 – Line Management and Talent Development**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module provides an overview of line management, including responsibilities, key skills, and the path to becoming a line manager. It examines what distinguishes good line managers from bad ones and addresses the common challenges they face, offering strategies for improvement. Additionally, this module also introduces talent development, explaining its importance, methods for identifying high-potential employees, and the roles of managers and HR in the process. It presents objectives, examples, strategies, and organizational benefits of effective talent development programs.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 - Line manager**
- Author: Żaneta Świątkowska-Warkocka
- Institution: Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Description of the video: This video defines the roles, explaining the responsibilities and functions of a line manager. It describes the key skills required for effective line management. The video also guides how to become a line manager, detailing the steps and qualifications needed to follow this career path.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 - How to be a good line manager?**
- Author: Żaneta Świątkowska-Warkocka
- Institution: Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Description of the video: This video focuses on the characteristics that separate good line managers from bad ones. The video looks at the common challenges that line managers face and suggests resources and strategies that can support line managers to be more effective in their roles.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 - Talent development**
- Author: Żaneta Świątkowska-Warkocka
- Institution: Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Description of the video: This video focuses on talent development. It explains what talent development is, and presents different methods of identifying high-potential employees. It presents the role of managers and HR in the talent identification process.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 4 – Goals, strategy, and benefits**
- Author: Żaneta Świątkowska-Warkocka
- Institution: Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Description of the video: This video highlights the differences between talent management and talent development. It presents the goals of talent development and examples of talent development initiatives. It discusses strategies for implementing effective talent development programs and the benefits these initiatives bring to organizations.

Number and title and of the module: **Module 13 – Communication**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module introduces essential communication skills for RMs, focusing on effective information exchange with both internal teams and external stakeholders. Key areas include relationship-building, designing communication plans, media liaison, social media engagement, and report writing.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE

- Number and title of the video: **Video 1 - Definition and Foundational Skills in Communication**
- Author: Marilou Ramos-Pamplona
- Institution: University of Liège
- Description of the video: This video defines communication within research management, detailing core skills such as relationship-building with stakeholders, crafting communication plans, and engaging with media to enhance research visibility and impact.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 2 - Building and Maintaining Relationships with Stakeholders: Introduction & Specific Situations**
- Author: Marilou Ramos-Pamplona
- Institution: University of Liège
- Description of the video: This video explores the role of stakeholders in research management, highlighting methods for building and sustaining relationships with researchers, funding agencies, institutional leaders, industry partners, and policymakers to support collaborative research environments.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 3 - Building and Maintaining Relationships with Stakeholders: Specific Challenges**
- Author: Marilou Ramos-Pamplona
- Institution: University of Liège
- Description of the video: This video addresses challenges in stakeholder relationships, including managing conflicting interests, overcoming communication barriers, and fostering engagement. It provides strategies to build trust, navigate power dynamics, and maintain ethical balance in research collaborations.

- Number and title of the video: **Video 4 - Building and Maintaining Relationships with Stakeholders: Characteristics to Develop**
- Author: Marilou Ramos-Pamplona
- Institution: University of Liège
- Description of the video: This video outlines key characteristics for effective stakeholder relationships, such as interpersonal skills, cultural competence, strategic thinking, ethical integrity, and collaboration. These traits are essential for fostering an inclusive and adaptable research environment.

Number and title and of the module: **Module 14 – Relationship Management**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module provides actionable insights on building and maintaining professional relationships essential for successful research project management. Aimed at early-career RMs (RM1), it covers effective communication, fostering both internal and external relationships with diverse stakeholders, and strategies for preventing and resolving conflicts. The module also highlights the unique dynamics of business-oriented research collaborations, with an emphasis on ethics, multicultural understanding, and professional diplomacy.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 1 - Trust, communication, relationships**
- Author: Ivona Peternel
- Institution: Juraj Dobrila University of Pula
- Video description: This training emphasizes the importance of cultivating trust, reliability, and clear communication within research partnerships and beyond. Key elements such as consistency, diplomacy, and mutual confidence are explored as foundations for strong, sustainable collaborations in research.

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 2 - Difficulties, cooperation with business**
- Author: Ivona Peternel
- Institution: Juraj Dobrila University of Pula
- Video description: This training provides insights into anticipating and managing potential challenges before they escalate, with a focus on research-business collaboration. It explores the contrasts in communication styles, expectations, and outcomes between the research and business communities, highlighting strategies for effective engagement and goal alignment.

Number and title and of the module: **Module 15 – Community Engagement**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE:

This module provides a comprehensive overview of community engagement strategies essential for effective research outreach and collaboration. Focusing on strengthening relationships with the academic community, engaging the broader public in research initiatives, and building connections with key stakeholders, the module prepares RMs with the necessary communication skills and tools for impactful engagement. Key topics include outreach communication, collaborative relationships with academic institutions, community involvement in research processes, stakeholder identification, and training for outreach skills.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 1- Research Outreach**
- Author: Elisabeth Lazarou
- Institution: Polytechnic University of Bucharest
- Description of the video: This video introduces Research Outreach, covering strategies to actively share research findings with the public. Topics include public presentations, educational materials development, and media engagement, aimed at making research accessible and impactful for diverse audiences.

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 2- Academic Community Relationship Collaboration**
- Author: Sanda Maiduc
- Institution: Polytechnic University of Bucharest
- Description of the video: This video explores collaboration within the academic community, focusing on partnerships with higher education institutions and research organizations. Methods for fostering these relationships include joint research projects, knowledge exchange, and student and staff mobility programs.

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 3 - Community Engagement with Research**
- Author: Sanda Maiduc
- Institution: Polytechnic University of Bucharest
- Description of the video: This training emphasizes the role of community input in guiding research through citizen science projects, advisory boards, focus groups, and surveys. The video also highlights aligning research with community needs and the United Nations' 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to enhance relevance and impact.

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 4 - Engagement with Key Stakeholders**
- Authors: Sanda Maiduc and Elisabeth Lazarou
- Institution: Polytechnic University of Bucharest
- Description of the video: This video demonstrates how to identify and connect with key stakeholders, such as policymakers, funding agencies, and community leaders, who can significantly influence and support your research endeavors.

- Number and title of the video: **Video number 5 - Provision of Training for Outreach Engagement**
- Author: Elisabeth Lazarou
- Institution: Polytechnic University of Bucharest
- Description of the video: In this final video, the focus is on equipping RMs with essential outreach skills. Training topics include effective communication and facilitation techniques, enabling RMs to engage more meaningfully with communities and other stakeholders.

Number and title and of the module: **Module 16 - How to embed the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) in the overall research management**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module introduces RMs to the *European Charter for Researchers*, which outlines the roles, responsibilities, and rights of researchers and their employers. It covers the *Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)* process—a framework for implementing the Charter and its principles within institutions—and provides guidance on integrating HRS4R into overall research management. The module also features a success story from University College Cork, demonstrating effective strategies for applying the Charter and its principles within research management.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE:

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 – What’s New – 4 Pillars – Gap Analysis Action Plan Coherence**
- Author: Mary Kate O'Regan
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This introductory video presents the module’s objectives and outlines the content, setting the stage for an in-depth exploration of the Charter and HRS4R.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 – OTMR**
- Author: Mary Kate O'Regan
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video introduces OTMR and related activities and what is expected in terms of achievement.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 – How to involve and engage stakeholders and researchers in the HRS4R process**
- Author: Mary Kate O'Regan
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: The video presents the advantages of HRS4R, the main HRS4R stakeholders, the benefits of involving stakeholders in the HRS4R process and how to engage your stakeholders.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 4 – Example of good practice**
- Author: Mary Kate O'Regan
- Institution: University College Cork
- Description of the video: This video presents University College Cork’s success story in implementing the Charter for Researchers. It details the methodology used to embed HRS4R within research management, offering a real-world example of effective practice.

Number and title and of the module: **Module 17 - Artificial intelligence in research management**

GENERAL CONTENT OF THE MODULE: This module provides RMs with an in-depth understanding of generative AI and its practical applications in research management. The course introduces AI basics, ethical and data safety considerations, advanced prompting techniques, and AI tool selection strategies, enabling managers to leverage AI tools effectively while ensuring compliance and ethical integrity in their workflows.

SYLLABUS OF THE MODULE

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 1 - Introduction to Generative AI and Basic Prompting**
- Author: Lionel Jouvét
- Institution: University of Southern Denmark
- Description of the video: This video introduces generative AI concepts and basic prompting techniques, highlighting the potential benefits and challenges of AI in research management. Key applications and current AI tools are discussed, alongside real-world examples of AI's role in report generation and summarization.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 2 - Ethical and Data Safety Considerations in AI**
- Author: Lionel Jouvét
- Institution: University of Southern Denmark
- Description of the video: Focusing on ethics and data safety, this video outlines critical concerns related to AI use, including bias, transparency, and GDPR compliance. Practical examples illustrate how to ensure AI tools are used responsibly and in line with data protection standards in research environments.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 3 - Advanced Prompting for Better AI Outputs**
- Author: Lionel Jouvét
- Institution: University of Southern Denmark
- Description of the video: This video explores advanced prompting techniques, such as multi-step and conditional prompts, to achieve tailored and high-quality AI outputs. RMs will learn to craft prompts that enhance AI's relevance and accuracy for project management tasks.

- Number and title and of the video: **Video number 4 - Choosing the Right AI Tools for Your Needs**
- Author: Lionel Jouvét
- Institution: University of Southern Denmark
- Description of the video: This video guides RMs through selecting appropriate AI tools based on functionality, security, scalability, and compliance needs. Insights into assessing AI tools for long-term viability and integration are provided to ensure informed, strategic tool choices.

REFERENCES

- CARDEA Competences Framework for RMs. <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/competenceframework/#rm-1-to-rm-4>
- CEDEFOP - European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (2013). Research Paper No 35. User guide to developing an employer survey on skill needs. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2013. doi:10.2816/413514
- Chiucconi, B., Feliziani, E., and Spigarelli, F. (2023). Training Catalogue - Initial suite (Versione 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731538>
- Chrualaioich J. U., and O'Regan M. K. (2023). Cardea (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7882908>
- Council of the European Union (2020). Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area. Brussels, 1 December 2020. <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13567-2020-INIT/en/pdf>
- Council of the European Union (2021). Council Recommendation on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe. Brussels, 26 November 2021. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/1a0df8ff-5313-11ec-91ac-01aa75ed71a1>
- Council of the European Union (2023). Council Recommendation of 18 December 2023 on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/C/2023/1640/oj>
- European Commission (2020). A New ERA for Research and Innovation. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Brussels, 30 September 2020. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-area_en
- European Commission (2020). European Skill Agenda. Brussels, July 2020. <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=89&newsId=9723&furtherNews=yes#navItem-1>
- European Commission (2020). Final report. A European approach to micro-credentials. Output of the micro-credential higher education consultation group. Brussels, December 2020. <https://education.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document-library-docs/european-approach-micro-credentials-higher-education-consultation-group-output-final-report.pdf>
- European Commission (2021). European Research Area Policy Agenda – Overview of actions for the period 2022-2024. Brussels, November 2021. https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf
- European Commission (2022). Proposal for a decision of the European Parliament and of the Council on a European Year of Skills 2023. Brussels, 12 October 2022. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-year-skills-2023_en
- Kerridge S., Scott S. (2017). Research Administration as a Profession (RAAAP) - A snapshot of research administrators and their skills from around the world. Poster. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.5278195.v1>
- Kerridge S., Scott S. (2018). *Research Administration around the World*. Research Management Review, 23 (1). pp. 1-34.
- Poli S., Kerridge S., Ajai-Ajagbe P. A., and Zornes D. (2023). Research management as labyrinthine - How and why people become and remain research managers and administrators around the world. In Kerridge S., Poli S., and Yang-Yoshihara M. (Eds.) *The Emerald Handbook of Research Management and Administration around the World*. Emerald Publishing. ISBN: 978-1-80382-701-8 (Online).
- Romano V. and Albanesi A. (2021). The role of the Research Manager and Administrator - RMA, in Italy: Professional framework and training needs 2020 Activity Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5513738>
- Romano V., Papadopoulos M., Vigtil A. (2022). Research support professionals and lifelong learning. The core activities of the professional development and recognition committee (PDRC) of EARMA. Conference paper, Oslo, EARMA Conference, 4-6 May, 2022. <https://earma.org/abstracts/submission/249/view/>

- Santos J. M. R. C. A., Varela C., and Kerridge S. (2021) Professionals at the interface of science: is there more than meets the eye?, *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 25:3, 100-105, DOI: [10.1080/13603108.2021.1881842](https://doi.org/10.1080/13603108.2021.1881842)
- Tauginiene L. (2009). *The Roles of a Research Administrator at a University*. *Viešoji politika ir administravimas/Public Policy and Administration*, Nr. 30, 45-56. <https://www.lituanistika.lt/content/23857>
- Virág E., Zsár V., and Balázs Z. (2019). Research Management and Administration: a profession still to be formalized. HETFA Discussion Paper supporting the framing and conceptualization of an educational programme for Research Managers and Administrators. pp. 1-48. https://hetfa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Research-managers_final_0408.pdf

Scientific literature concerning the definition of the professional figure of RM

- Andersen J. (2011). What is research administration, and who is the research administrator.
- Andersen J., Poli S., Toom K., and Miller P. F. (2018). *Research Management: Europe and Beyond*. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2015-0-00323-9>
- Müller U., Toczyski P., Regös N., Pliszczynska O., and Jankovics R. (2022). Professionalization of science management—Comparing formal education and training across Germany, Poland, and Hungary - *Frontiers of Higher Education*.
- Green J., and Langley D. (2009). Professionalising Research Management. <https://snowballmetrics.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/2009-professionalising-research-management-2.pdf>
- Virágh E., Zsár V., and Balázs Z. (2020). *Research Management and Administration: The relevance of specific education and training programmes*.
- Agostinho M., Moniz Alves C., Aresta S., Borrego F., Borlido-Santos J., Cortez J., Lima Costa T., Lopes J. A., Moreira S., Santos J., Trindade M., Varela C, and Vidal S. (2018). The interface of science: the case for a broader definition of research management, *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*.
- Stackhouse J. (2008). Profiling the profession. *Research Global*, 19, 8–9, 22.
- Williamson C., Dyason K., and Jackson J. (2020). Scaling up Professionalization of Research Management in Southern Africa. *Journal of Research Administration*, 34(1), 88–98.
- Derrick G., and Nickson A. (2014). Invisible intermediaries: A systematic review into the role of research management in university and institutional research processes. *Journal of Research Administration*, 45(2), 11-45.
- Hockey J., and Allen-Collinson J. (2009). Occupational knowledge and practice amongst UK university research administrators. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 63(2), 141-159.
- Poli S., Andersen J., Toom K., and Wilkman L. (2014). Shaping a new profession in higher education and research institutions. *NCURA Magazine*, August 54-56.
- Shelley L. (2010). Research managers uncovered: Changing roles and ‘shifting arenas’ in the academy. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 64(1), 41-64.
- Waite J. (2011). Research Administrators as Servant Leaders. *Journal of Research Administration*, 42(2), 64-77.
- Whitchurch C. (2008). *Professional Managers in HE: Preparing for Complex Futures*. LFHEreport
- Williamson C., Dyason K., and Jackson J. (2020). Scaling up Professionalization of Research Management in Southern Africa. *Journal of Research Administration*, 51(1), 46-72.
- Shambrook J., Roberts T. J. (2011). 2010 Profile of a Research Administrator. *Research Management Review*, 18 (1), 19-30.
- Shambrook, J., Lasrado, V., Roberts, T. J., O’Neal, T. (2015). 2015 Profile of a Research Administrator. *SRA International*.

Competences frameworks organizing RM’s competences and related skills.

- ARMA Professional Development Framework for Research Managers and Administrators⁵².
- Ritain project developed framework for managers of research infrastructures⁵³.
- Italian professional framework for RMs developed within a working group of CODAU (Association of General Directors of Italian Universities)⁵⁴.
- CARDEA RM professional framework⁵⁵

⁵² <https://arma.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/PDF-Final.pdf>

⁵³ <http://ritrain.eu/competency-profile>

⁵⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/5513738>

⁵⁵ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/competenceframework/>

